

Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

D6.2

Contact us

www.bluerevproject.eu

info@bluerevproject.eu

 @BlueRevEU

D6.2

Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities

DELIVERABLE TYPE

Document, report

MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY

Month 18, February 2024

WORK PACKAGE

WP 6

LEADER

LOBA

DISSEMINATION LEVEL

Public

AUTHOR(S)

Joana Oliveira
Mariana Carneiro
Ilaria Bientinesi

DOI / ISBN

10.5281/zenodo.10604265

Programme	Contract Number	Duration	Start
Horizon Europe	101060537	36 Months	September 2022

Contributors

Name

Alexandros Koukovinis
Ilaria Bientinesi
Concetta M. Messina

Organisation

LOBA
APRE
UniPa

Reviewers

Name

Mariana Carneiro
Candela Bravo
Alessia Careccia
Alexandros Koukovinis

Organisation

LOBA
LOBA
APRE
LOBA

Revision History

Version	Date	Reviewer	Modifications
0.1	09/01/2024	Joana Oliveira	First version
0.2	23/01/2024	Mariana Carneiro	Review and suggestions
0.3	30/01/2024	Candela Bravo	Proof reading
0.4	26/02/2024	All consortium	Consortium inputs
0.5	27/02/2024	Candela Bravo	Final adjustments
1.0	28/02/2024	Alexandros Koukovinis	Final review

The information and views set out in this report are those of the author(s) and do not necessarily reflect the official opinion of the European Union. Neither the European Union institutions and bodies nor any person acting on their behalf.

Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms

Abbreviation	Meaning
EU	European Union
DC	Dissemination & Communication
IPR	Intellectual Property Rights
IP	Intellectual Property
KPIs	Key Performance Indicators
SMA s	Social Media Accounts
SME s	Small and Medium Enterprises
NGO s	Non-governmental Organisations
PPT	PowerPoint
PR	Press Release
DoA	Description of Action
SEO	Search Engine Optimisation
SERP s	Search Engine Results Pages
WP	Work Package
LCA	Live Cycle Assessment
LMS	Learning Management System
CA	Consortium Agreement
BG	Background
FG	Foreground
ER	Exploitable Results
NDA	Non-disclosure Agreement
R&D	Research and Development

Index of Contents

1	Executive Summary	9
2	Introduction	10
3	Updates to the Dissemination and Communication Plan	11
3.1	Overview and evaluation of the initial dissemination and communication plan core elements.....	13
3.2	Key performance Indicators of the First Period	20
4	Status assessment and Updates to the DC strategy	22
4.1	Channels updates	22
4.1.1	Website	22
4.1.2	Social Media channels.....	25
4.1.3	Newsletters and subscribers.....	29
4.2	Tools and materials	30
4.2.1	Communication KIT	30
4.2.2	Actionable knowledge.....	31
4.3	Collaboration with other projects and initiatives	32
4.4	Updates in the communication of external and internal events	34
5	Support Tool	37
5.1	Technical sheet for the Support Tool	38
5.1.1	Introduction to the platform and the technology used.....	38
5.1.2	Structure and functionalities of the BlueRev Support Tool	39
6	Update Exploitation and Sustainability Initial Guidelines	43
6.1	Introduction	43
6.2	Adopted definitions	43
6.2.1	Exploitation.....	43
6.2.2	Valorisation.....	44
6.2.3	Sustainability	44
6.3	Purpose of the Exploitation guidelines	45
6.4	Target audiences.....	46
6.5	IPR Management Strategy	47
6.5.1	Definitions.....	48
6.6	IPR Approach during the Implementation Stage	53

6.7	IPR Conflicts	55
6.8	IPR Matrix Methodology	56
6.8.1	Identification of Background IP	57
6.8.2	Identification of Foreground IP	58
6.8.3	Identification of Exploitable results.....	59
6.9	IPR Matrix identified	61
6.10	Re-cap of the BlueRev promo-toolkit	61
6.10.1	Website & Support tool	62
6.10.2	Social media networks.....	63
6.10.3	Briefings, Leaflets, and brochure	63
6.10.4	Participation in Events, Workshops, and Conferences.....	63
6.10.5	Partners' networks	63
6.10.6	Further improvement of project results.....	63
6.11	Action suggestions for the partnership.....	63
6.11.1	Transfer and follow-up projects.....	64
6.11.2	Sustainability	64
6.11.3	Accreditation and formal recognition of training	64
6.11.4	Networking/Lobbying	64
6.11.5	Develop New Partnerships	65
6.12	Keep this in mind!.....	65
7	Conclusions	67
8	Appendix.....	68
	Appendix A – Brand Manual.....	68
	Appendix B – Deliverable template.....	71
	Appendix C – PowerPoint template	72
	Appendix D – Project brochure.....	73
	Appendix E – Project Poster.....	74
	Appendix F – Project promo card	75
	Appendix G – Project Roll Up.....	76
	Appendix H – Project presentation	77
	Appendix I – Project stationery kit	79
	Appendix L – IPR Matrix (M18).....	80

Index of Tables

Index of tables

Table 1: Evaluation of initial framework set up for the dissemination and communication	13
Table 2: Progress against the KPIs	20
Table 3: BlueRev’s website global statistics	22
Table 4: Acquisition channels for the project’s website	23
Table 5: Website’s most visited pages	23
Table 6: Overview of the META channels’ statistics	26
Table 7: Overview of LinkedIn statistics	27
Table 8: Overview of X statistics	27
Table 9: Overview of Youtube statistics	28
Table 10: List of the already established collaborations	32
Table 11: List of internal events	34
Table 12: List of external events	35
Table 13: List of potential events	36
Table 14: Access Rights	49
Table 15: Indicative list of protection instruments	54
Table 16: Structure of the IPR Matrix	56
Table 17: IPR Matrix Background Template	57
Table 18: IPR Matrix Foreground Template	58
Table 19: IPR Matrix Exploitable Results Template	60

Index of Figures

Figure 1: Support tool footer	38
Figure 2: BlueRev target groups clustering	46
Figure 3: The BlueRev stages of IPR definition and implementation	47
Figure 4: CDE schematic	62

1 Executive Summary

This deliverable aims to present an updated version of the plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities and the associated actions that will be implemented during the BlueRev project. This document also presents an overview of the actions implemented during the first year of the project in comparison with the initial version of the dissemination & communication plan (D6.1 – Month 6). It builds on the original strategy set in M6, conducting an evaluation of the activities undertaken in the first year of the project and describing the focus of the dissemination during the second and third year.

In collaboration with Task 6.5, led by APRE (Exploitation manager), the present deliverable addresses the update plan for the exploitation and sustainability strategy, aiming at ensuring the timely promotion of the project's outcomes and engagement of parties outside the Consortium, interested in using or adopting them.

In addition, this deliverable describes the updated action plan for support tool that will enable the BlueRev stakeholders to operate within the project goals of Piloting. The online tool is referred to as the result of the Task 2.3 Support tool (Task leader: LOBA, Partners involved: all) (M1-M36) but it was decided by the partnership, since it is developed by LOBA, that its initial steps (development, function etc) can be integrated in the CD&E deliverables.

The leader of WP6 (LOBA) is responsible for:

- the overall management and support of the activities defined under the present dissemination and communication plan and develop the main tools and materials to be used for the implementation of the plan.
- monitor the dissemination and communication activities, assessing the performance and identifying necessary corrective measures.

All the partners are also actively involved in conducting the assigned dissemination and communication actions and are highly committed to ensure a satisfactory dissemination of the project results. In general, the partners' expected contribution is to:

- a) support the communication and dissemination of the project with activities in their own countries among their contacts and networks;
- b) provide news and updates for the website and newsletter;
- c) help to keep the project's social media accounts (SMAs) alive and active, by suggesting/providing relevant content to be posted on BlueRev social media by LOBA, and to post relevant content about the project on their own channels mentioning @BLUEREVEU;
- d) Participate in relevant events to promote the project and its outcomes;
- e) Contribute to the scientific papers mentioning the R4EU project.

2 Introduction

This document constitutes the outcome of D6.2 “Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities”, which is part of WP6 “Dissemination & Communication, Exploitation and Replication”. The revised plan aims to review the project’s Dissemination and Communication objectives, the strategy that is followed to meet the objectives and the means, channels, and tools used during this process to optimise the effect of BlueRev. The updated plan outlines all the Communication and Dissemination activities and tools and shows a fully developed picture of the project’s strategy for the remaining project’s duration.

Therefore, the document consists of six main chapters, where the scheme below is being elaborated:

- **Chapter 1:** Executive Summary
- **Chapter 2:** Introduction and objectives of the updated strategy
- **Chapter 3:** Overview and analysis of the initial Dissemination and Communication plan
- **Chapter 4:** Evaluation of the first period evaluation criteria (KPIs) and updates to the strategy in terms of communication to target groups, channels, tools, materials, and communication of internal external events.
- **Chapter 5:** Updates to the support tool developments
- **Chapter 6:** Update to the Exploitation strategy

3 Updates to the Dissemination and Communication Plan

The core objective for disseminating the BlueRev project and the respective key performance indicators have not changed from the initial plan for Dissemination and Communication (see Deliverable D6.1). Therefore, the objectives continue to be:

- Raise awareness of the project's activities and events;
- Engage relevant target groups and stakeholders to get involved in the project's activities that will be implemented around the main action pillars of the project;
- Communicate and disseminate the results of the project among the main target groups;
- Make use of a variety of channels to efficiently communicate the project amongst the main target groups;
- Develop printed support materials (such as posters, roll-ups, stationary, etc.) and digital materials (videos, infographics, etc.) when necessary, but also be environmentally conscious in the production of printed materials;
- Create a link to other existing projects that deal with Entrepreneurship, Business, Education and Policy in the Blue Economy (in connection with T2.1);
- Ensure regular communication to keep the target groups, the media and other projects/initiatives updated on the project, through emailing, press releases and newsletters.

In its first year, when the project just started with its activities and there was not much content yet stemming from the project's activities, the communication strategy focused on establishing appropriate conditions for successful dissemination. This included developing the initial strategy, defining a unique identity for the project, setting up relevant tools and channels to be used during the project and start creating awareness about the project and thereby start building up a community of stakeholders and target groups. As soon as the first findings and results were coming out from project activities, the objective of the dissemination shifted towards ensuring that these were communicated throughout the project's channels.

In its second year, the project is more mature and reached a stage where most of the activities are ongoing. Therefore, the communication strategy needs to shift its focus on maintaining a continuous and steady dissemination (promoting the preliminary results of the project directing traffic to the website, animating social networks, participate/organize events, etc.), aiming to continuously create and increase the awareness and interest around the project results and engage stakeholders in the project activities/events.

In the last stage, towards the end of the project, when most activities are being finalized and the majority of results will be available, the communication and dissemination strategy should focus on intensifying the dissemination towards exploitation and

sustainability and contribute by actively “selling” the benefits of the results to the potential end users and stakeholders, contributing towards the sustainability and exploitation.

3.1 Overview and evaluation of the initial dissemination and communication plan core elements

In Table 1 below we present an overview with the general comparison of what was defined in the first dissemination and communication plan and a succinct analysis and assessment of the activities performed in the first 18 months, which will then be detailed in chapter 4.

Table 1: Evaluation of initial framework set up for the dissemination and communication

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
Identity	The identity comprises the noticeable elements of a brand (for instance - trademark colour, logo, name, symbol). It is what identifies and differentiates a brand in the target audience's mind. Identity guidelines also created, to help all contributing counterparts to stay close to the BlueRev identity and work as supporting material for the daily creation of dissemination and communication materials	The identity created for BlueRev provided a cohesive visual identity for the project. All elements of the identity have been used appropriately and successfully implemented in all materials produced in the project such as templates, brochures, website, support tool, posters, communication material, roll-up, banners, and videos, etc.	The identity has been solidified and proved to be sufficient and appropriate for the project. Thus there is not a foreseeable need to adjust for the coming period.
Target groups	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • National, regional, local authorities and regional clusters; • Primary biomass producers, associations, and cooperatives; • Organisations and SMEs; 	The list of target groups defined for the project continues to be accurate and relevant. For each target group the project defined the core reason for targeting them,	Going forward, more campaigns, actionable knowledge, materials, tools, and videos will be

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Civil society organisations including NGOs; • Knowledge providers and scientific communities; • Marginalised groups 	<p>the drivers and motivations and channels to reach them. Taking this into account, the project has the capacity of providing diverse content considered relevant for each target group.</p>	<p>implemented, addressing each different target group.</p>
<p>Channels 1) Website</p>	<p>The project website is the main window of information access and contact for the interested stakeholders. It has been designed to integrate a multi-communication approach with several “hooks” to engage the user in further engagement.</p>	<p>An initial version of the website (splash page) was launched on M2, followed by the official version on M4 in line with Milestone 7 “Full project website”. It has been regularly updated since then. Partners have been producing regular content for the news and articles section and good results have been achieved with the users being interested in visiting the website. Additionally, the page that lists the related projects and initiatives has also been a good effort to disseminate further initiatives and to initiate the collaboration with different projects. The website also informs and re-directs users to the support tool.</p>	<p>Increase website visitors through a combination of strategies to improve the website visibility, reach and engagement. Intensify the content production also, with news of the project and events that can create a buzz and keep it alive.</p>

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
Channels 2) Social Media	<p>The Project has decided to use a variety of social media and adjust the communication messages to reflect the audience caption in every mean. The social media channels chosen for the project are: X Facebook LinkedIn Instagram YouTube</p>	<p>These accounts have been regularly updated with 1 or 2 posts per week, plus additional shares, and retweets. Several performance campaigns have been designed to help the project reach itKPIs. A significant effort has also been made in the social media accounts to direct traffic to the website and support tool. At the moment the YouTube channel serves as a video catalogue that hosts the 2 videos developed so far.</p>	<p>Increase the amount of performance campaigns to grow the number of followers. Continue the efforts to direct traffic to the website and support tool.</p>

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
Channels 3) Events	<p>Events is a valuable component of the C&D strategy because it supports the building of important relations with the project stakeholders. The C&D strategy included a future planning of events but also monitoring tools and suggestions to the partners.</p>	<p>Partners have participated in 12 events to promote the project, and an audience of 3085 people has met the project through these events.</p>	<p>Continue to provide support to all partners participating in events. Widely promote the participation using the projects channels. Also, intensify the intra-project sharing of relative events in order to boost a joint participation.</p>
Channels 4) Mailing List	<p>The dedicated mailing list is a tool that can help build a database of loyal followers that are inclined to engage more in the project. Thus, it is an important element to complement the website interactive functions.</p>	<p>The mailing list where newsletters have been sent has also exponentially increased due to the promotion activities.</p>	<p>Increase the number of newsletters dispatched and widely promote them. Constant update of the project's mailing lists.</p>

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
Promotional Tools	1) Supporting tools and materials: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication toolkit (i.e. PPT Templates, Stationery (Folder, Letterhead Paper, etc) • Promotional materials (Brochure, Poster / Roll Up) • Project presentation • Promotional videos 	<p>Several supporting dissemination and communication materials have been created such as stationary (PPT; Word; Letterhead Paper) promotional materials (Brochure; Poster; Project Presentation; Roll Up) and communication tool kit (Lanyard; Background for Conferences; Email Signature; Folder; Business Card; Promo Card). All these materials were essential to promote the project through the already created channels but also at events. Two videos presenting the project have also been created and disseminated in all project channels.</p>	<p>Continue to create and update the several supporting dissemination and communication materials.</p>

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
	<p>2) Additional communication activities:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Newsletter 	<p>Additional communication activities consist of the distribution of annual newsletter, which was dispatched to the mailing list, disseminated on the website, and promoted on social media channels. It informed the public about the different stages of the project, its expected results and highlighted the launch of the support tool.</p>	<p>Increase the number of newsletters dispatched and widely promote them. Create Press Releases to communicate key events and milestones of the project</p>
<p>Excel for monitoring performance and reporting</p>	<p>The monitoring and reporting excel is a shared document where partners are requested to update the information related to the Dissemination and Communication activities implemented. The excel is divided into these spreadsheets:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Communication and Dissemination activities – to monitor the impact from 	<p>Partners have used this monitoring and reporting procedure during the first period, and they will continue to use it throughout the project. Occasional reminders have been sent to partners to keep the information updated.</p>	<p>Increase the number of reminders to guarantee a successful monitoring of activities.</p>

Component	Actions, channels & tools defined in the DC Plan	Summary evaluation of the first 18 months	Approach and directions to follow for the next 18 months
	<p>events organised by the project partners and the participation in external events organised by third parties as well as other activities implemented through organisation or personal channels.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scientific publications – to monitor the scientific outputs developed by project partners. 		

3.2 Key performance Indicators of the First Period

This section presents an overview of the performance of the Dissemination and Communication activities implemented during the first 18 months of the project. Therefore, the Table 2 presents the Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) against the status. These KPIs are in alignment with the overall project’s KPIs stipulated in Description of Action (DoA) and D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities.

This information will help to assess necessary improvements or adjustments in the strategy.

Table 2: Progress against the KPIs

Tools and channels	Metric method	Expected results at M36	Actual results (M18)	Status
Website	Number of website visitors	10,000	3547	35,47%
Promotional materials	Number of Project logos	1	1	Achieved
	Number of leaflets produced	1	1	Achieved
	Number of brochures produced	1	1	Achieved
	Number of posters produced	1	1	Achieved
Social media	Number of followers	1000	Total: 819 X: 198 Facebook:334 Instagram:160 LinkedIn: 113	81,90%
Press Releases	Number of press releases	6	1	Ongoing
Newsletters and Mailing List	Number newsletters	6	1	Ongoing
	Number of subscribers	500	44	Ongoing
Promotional videos	Number of videos	1	2	Achieved

	Number of views	2000	12202	Achieved
Scientific Publications	Number of publications	12	-	To start
	Number of readers	2000	-	To start
Participation in external events	Number of presentations in external events	12	12	Achieved
	Number of attendees	3000	3080	Achieved
Workshops and training programmes	Number of workshops	9	2	Ongoing
	Number of training programmes	1	-	To start
	Number of modules	4	-	To start
	Number of lessons	13	-	To start
	Number of stakeholders	500	-	To start
Leveraging BlueRev partners networks	Number of recipients	3000	600	On going

As seen in the table the green colour on the KPI status indicates a high performance so far, in line with achieving and even overcoming in the future the goals set. . From the analysis, it is noted that higher efforts should be put in producing and publishing scientific papers, as well as make use of channels that are performing very well to redirect to the ones that still need higher achievements. Additionally, now that the project will pursue a higher maturity level, results will be available and will allow new workshops and trainings to start, and actionable knowledge stemming from these results will boost the engagement and interest in the project.

4 Status assessment and Updates to the DC strategy

4.1 Channels updates

This section provides an overview of the performance on dissemination and communication activities implemented in BlueRev during this period and it will link the upcoming activities of the project together with materials and tools currently under development or planned for the 2nd half of the project. The purpose of this exercise is to ensure a proper communication of these activities, tools and materials, and the engagement of respective target groups.

4.1.1 Website

The website was developed and launched during the 1st year of the project, first as a splash page in M2, then turning into the official website in M4. For the first few months, the website hosted basic information about the project, and during the project progression it was enriched with activities of the project, milestones achieved, articles & news posts and workshops/events published. All the consequent posts made on social media have been leading to the website of the project to augment the traffic and make more people aware of the online point of access to the BlueRev world.

Below follow the website statistics for the first period of the project.

Table 3: BlueRev's website global statistics

BlueRev's website global analysis					
Users	Page views	User engagement	Engagement rate	Downloads	Countries
3,547	11,097	7,450	50.80%	87	48

Top ten countries:

1. Ukraine – 1043 users
2. Portugal – 412 users
3. Greece – 379 users
4. United States – 299 users
5. Italy – 266 users
6. Germany – 151 users
7. Netherlands – 67 users
8. Norway – 63 users
9. Sweden – 55 users
10. Albania – 43 users

Top acquisition channels:

Acquisition analytics show data about how users arrive on your website. The traffic sources can be:

- Direct: any traffic where the referrer or source is unknown,
- Organic search: traffic from search engine results that originate from paid advertising,
- Organic social: Traffic from a social network, such as Facebook, LinkedIn, X,
- Referral: traffic that occurs when a user finds the website through a site other than a major search engine,
- Email: Traffic from email marketing that has been properly tagged with an email parameter,
- Other: If traffic does not fit into another source or has been tagged as “Other” via a URL parameter, it will be bucketed into “Other” traffic.

The following table shows the acquisition channels applied to the BlueRev’s website.

Table 4: Acquisition channels for the project’s website

Channel	Triggered session	
Direct	1568	
Organic Social	1261	
	Meta	1158
	LinkedIn	49
	X	54
Organic Search	281	
Referral	154	
Email	94	
Paid social	7	
Other	9	

As it can be seen in the table above, the channel that triggers the most sessions is direct traffic, followed by social media, particularly the META channels.

Most visited pages:

Table 5: Website’s most visited pages

Page	Number of views
Newsletter	1347
Home page	1044
Consortium	328
News & article	320

Based on the analysis of Key Performance Indicators the traffic to the website is not following the expectations for the 1st period. This can be easily explained by the level of maturity of the project, as most results will be happening the 2nd period of the project and will boost the project channels. Therefore, the presented numbers should grow organically during the 2nd period of the project, due to the increased number of results, events and workshops that will be available on the website. Furthermore, direct traffic (referrals) to the website will continue to be encouraged via social networks. Special attention will be given to properly valorising the results stemming from WP2, WP3, WP4, and WP5, with the development of factsheets, infographics, and short videos that highlight key insights.

Next steps:

The following steps and measures will be taken to ensure that the project achieves the KPIs. Increasing website visitors involves a combination of strategies to improve the site's visibility, reach, and engagement.

- **Analyse the current Search Engine Optimisation (SEO) and adjust, if necessary, by:**
 - Improving our ranking on search engine results pages (SERPs);
 - Using relevant keywords in your content, meta tags, and headers;
 - Creating high-quality, valuable content;
 - Update website content frequently.
- **Implement a more precise content strategy by:**
 - Uploading more news articles; results stemming from WPs (infographics; leaflets; brochures; booklets; posters; etc).
- **Make use of other channels to promote the website with a wider audience by:**
 - Ensuring the inclusion of call to actions on the social media channels redirecting to the website;
 - Analysing the possibility of paid campaigns on social media channels to increase visibility and reach specific target groups;
 - Reaching out to existing networks to promote the website and the project;
 - Using more frequently email marketing to reach wider audiences.
- **Build and maintain an email list to nurture relationships with BlueRev audience by:**
 - Sending regular newsletters, updates, and project results to keep our audience engaged;

- Adopting flash news email marketing to keep the audience engaged between newsletters launches.
- **Make an effort to keep the website user-friendly by:**
 - Ensuring the project website is easy to navigate and provides a positive user experience;
 - Ensuring the website is optimised for mobile devices, as a significant portion of internet users access websites from smartphones and tablets.
- **Implement influencer Marketing by:**
 - Reaching out to promote possible collaborations with existing networks in the blue bio-based economy to reach their followers and tap into their established audience.
- **Increase Networking by:**
 - Promoting the website and other channels when attending external events, conferences, and webinars to connect with other stakeholders.
- **Optimise Website Speed by:**
 - Analysing and adjusting the website's loading speed, as slow websites can lead to higher bounce rates.
- **Analytics and Data Analysis:**
 - Continue using tools like Google Analytics to understand the website traffic, user behaviour, and areas of improvement;
 - Ensure that this analysis is made monthly to guarantee that the strategy is working and adjust if necessary.

4.1.2 Social Media channels

The official social networks of BlueRev were launched in M2 on Meta: [Facebook](#) and [Instagram](#), [X](#), and [LinkedIn](#). A [YouTube](#) channel has been established as well. The creation of social media channels entailed:

- Define an appropriate handle @BLUEREVEU;
- Design and upload of the cover and profile images;
- Design of frame templates to include pictures in publications;
- Design of frame templates for heading posts;
- Research relevant content for our audiences, both from internal sources (within the project) and external (sources outside the project) and develop the posts.

Each month a social media plan is designed with the weekly publications for each social media channel. Between 1 to 3 publications are created per week in each channel, which entail creating images and content for each publication. Additional posts are also added to the social media plan whenever there is new information (events, activities, announcements) about the project that should be communicated. At the same time, a lot of attention is given to the engagement and reach on social media channels, continuously retweeting/sharing and interacting with other accounts, especially from European Commission channels and other relevant projects and initiatives.

The focus of the content published on social media has evolved in line with the progress of the project, going from creating awareness about what BlueRev is and what the project has to offer, to communicating specific activities, events, and results. Thus, social media has focused on the following communication objectives:

- to inform about BlueRev, our objectives and main activities;
- to inform about the pilot regions;
- to provide information related to the blue bio-based sector;
- to inform about events; workshops; webinars that the project is involved in;
- to support the communication of activities and events from other sister projects and related projects;
- to inform and promote the project support tool;
- to engage our audience towards specific activities carried out in the project with dedicated campaigns;
- to disseminate the BlueRev Newsletter and encourage subscribing to the project's mailing list;

Overview of the Social Media channels' performance and results

Table 6: Overview of the META channels' statistics

META				
Followers	Link clicks	Engagement	Reach	Impressions
494	7,390	72,541	1,169,918	1,534,269

The META media channels are considered high-flow social networks and so they tend to bring better results. The investment between the two media was €986.11 (46.1% of the total investment in social media campaigns) with a good balance of investment, reach, and impressions. Regarding engagement, the highlight is Instagram, while Facebook tends to have more clicks that lead to the website.

In these channels, 21 campaigns were implemented on Facebook and 22 on Instagram. Between campaigns, when the objective is to attract followers, Facebook's results are better than Instagram's. Engagement campaigns reflect better numbers on Instagram. Click campaigns work better on Facebook.

At the moment, the Meta channels (Facebook and Instagram) represent, respectively, 40.8% and 19.5% of BlueRev's follower base.

Table 7: Overview of LinkedIn statistics

LinkedIn				
Followers	Link clicks	Engagement	Reach	Impressions
113	1,041	1,895	42,656	71,002

We have great results on LinkedIn with an investment in campaigns of €655.19 (30.6% of the total investment in social media campaigns). We ran 2 campaigns, one for followers and the other for new subscribers to the newsletter.

Organically, the network has lower representation, however, it focuses on specific target groups closely related to the project due to their knowledge and influence in the blue bio-based sector.

LinkedIn tends to be the smallest network numerically speaking, but it's where the highest quality interactions come from. It is also an expensive network to advertise on, but it also converts results that are durable for the project. As this is considered a more professional network, the interactions and engagement are very important for the project, and we can assume that when there is a new follower or a comment on any publication, there is real interest and impact achieved.

In the announcements made, the new followers' campaign performed well, bringing 29 new followers at a unit cost of €6.66 per follower. Regarding the promotion and new subscribers for the newsletter campaign, the results were not relevant, which can easily be explained by the fact that the project hasn't launched sufficient newsletters to generate significant buzz and interest in the subscription for the newsletter.

This social network represents 13.8% of BlueRev's follower base.

Table 8: Overview of X statistics

X				
Followers	Link clicks	Engagement	Reach	Impressions
198	3,561	6,289	2,175,853	3,285,033

Despite the setbacks of 2023, X delivers reach and impressions in very high numbers, however, with lower overall interaction rates. The investment was €499.02 (23.3% of the total investment in social media campaigns) with 25 campaigns in total.

Organically, it is the social network that generates the most clicks on recommended links.

When we talk about interaction, X is a considerable force, representing more than 57% of the actions in the project. Due to the ease of replication and response, it tends to be a network with a high volume of deliveries, however, it has suffered in recent months with the loss of users and changes that affect both usability and trust.

Followers and link click campaigns conducted on X perform better than engagement campaigns, which despite presenting higher numbers, the data does not seem to corroborate reality.

We continue to see it as an important aspect in a digital strategy, but investment in the platform can be reallocated to more reliable social networks.

The social network represents 24.2% of BlueRev's follower base.

Table 9: Overview of Youtube statistics

Youtube				
Followers	Thruplays	Engagement	Reach	Impressions
14	53	N/A	N/A	N/A

At the moment, the social network only serves as a video catalogue, with few exclusive actions. There is a strength to be explored on the network with more videos, cuts, and invitations, on other social networks, for people to follow the BlueRev channel on YouTube. We expect to be able to explore this opportunity in the 2nd period of the project when more results will be stemming from the different WPs, and we will implement a more frequent content creation for this network.

It represents only 1.7% of the project's followers.

Next steps

The current social networks being used in the project are suitable and have their own unique potential as previously described. However, it's important to note that these platforms typically require a higher frequency of posts and more active community management in order to achieve better results.

Using LinkedIn as a sending method for newsletters can enhance subscriptions and deliver the articles to the subscriber's emails.

At present, the adoption of Threads is still in its initial stages. X is well-suited for the microblogging format, while the new tool has not yet gained widespread usage. However, if the situation changes in X, migration to Threads can be considered in future planning.

To achieve our KPIs and build a community of genuinely interested people with BlueRev, we need to focus on two areas: followers and website traffic. For the campaigns, we require a fixed strategy throughout the year to build followers. Secondly, we must concentrate on website traffic by creating monthly posts, which should be changed

regularly to keep the audience engaged. By doing so, we can easily achieve our KPIs and surpass them.

Engagement campaigns can be created with less investment to keep posts alive on social networks.

Content wise, some of the topics that the project will communicate during the 2nd period on social media channels are:

- Preliminary results from the interviews and workshops developed in the pilot regions;
- LCA reports developed in the pilot region;
- New developments in the support tool, the webinars and the new courses and training module available;
- New synergies and related projects;
- Best practices developed in the 3 pilot regions;
- New models for social innovations; new business models and new governance models being developed within the project;
- Multimedia contents and demonstrative videos that will be developed within the best practices;

4.1.3 Newsletters and subscribers

The first project newsletter was launched in January 2024, and was distributed to the project's mailing lists.

The first newsletter issue was promoted in all the project channels and by partners through their networks/channels. All articles are also included on the website and promoted individually.

The goal of the first newsletter ([link](#)) was to welcome subscribers to the project and inform them about the main activities undertaken and results gathered so far, as well as generate interest in future activities.

At the moment the subscribers' mailing list has 42 members and the internal project mailing list has 34 members.

BlueRev's 1 st newsletter analysis			
Sent	Delivered	Opened	Clicked
42	42	25	3

Next steps:

To achieve the KPI of 500 subscribers we will have to take new action points to help generate buzz around the project, and have people be organically interested in subscribing to the project mailing list. These points are:

- Implement a more structured strategy for each newsletter, defining the more relevant topics, the corresponding authors and a tentative timeline;
- Increase the number and frequency of newsletters;
- Develop flash news emails campaigns (small newsletter) focused on specific points and results to reach specific target groups. These flash news email campaigns will be launched in between newsletter issues;
- Increase the social media channels communication regarding this topic to help publicise the project and generate interest in subscribing to the mailing list;
- Increase the effort on events to evoke interest of stakeholders to subscribe;
- Communicate our newsletter launches and news flashes emails to our sister and related projects so they can communicate it on their networks, and consequently reach a wider audience.

4.2 Tools and materials

This section describes the updates in the tools and materials to be implemented during the 2nd period of the project.

4.2.1 Communication KIT

The communication kit comprises materials that assist the consortium with successful dissemination and communication of the project activities, as well as with the promotion of the brand identity, making it memorable. All materials depict at least the BlueRev website URL and the EU flag. They are:

- Project identity
 - Logo
 - Graphic kit
 - Brand manual (appendix A)
- Project's stationary
 - Word template for deliverables creation (Appendix B)
 - PowerPoint template (Appendix C)
 - Folder (Appendix I)
 - Letter head paper (Appendix I)
 - Email signatures (Appendix I)
 - Background for online meetings (Appendix I)
 - Business cards (Appendix I)

- 1st communication Kit
 - Initial brochure (Appendix D)
 - Poster (Appendix E)
 - Project presentation (Appendix H)
 - Promo card (Appendix F)
 - Roll up (Appendix G)
- Multimedia content
 - Teaser video ([LINK](#))
 - Project presentation video ([LINK](#))

Next steps:

As the project is entering a different maturity level, we believe the communication kit should be updated with a more recent version of materials, to already include preliminary results. These new materials will be essential for the dissemination of project results, as so we propose the following:

- 2nd communication kit
 - Updated brochure or leaflet;
 - Updated project presentation;
 - Brochure per pilot region with preliminary analysis.
- Workshop and events info pack
 - Agenda template;
 - Images and banners for news articles and social media channels;
 - Invitation template;
 - Poster template.
- Videos
 - Videos of the workshop entailing the main results;
 - Videos featuring interviews with relevant stakeholders;
 - Short animations to showcase key findings and results;
 - Video with the best practices and lesson learnings.

4.2.2 Actionable knowledge

In the 2nd period of the time, a special effort will be done in creating actionable knowledge that will boost the communication and dissemination of the project. The actionable knowledge material of results stemming from the project WPs planned to be created is:

- Infographic of the framework for mapping the current governance structures, business models and social innovations linked to the implemented pilot regions (D3.1);
- Factsheet on LCA report on the pilot regions (D3.5);
- Factsheet on report on the governance models in the pilot regions (D3.4);
- Infographic on the business models analysis (D3.6);
- Factsheet on new models for social innovations to enable stakeholders to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviour (D4.1);
- Booklet on the best practices guideline including the best practices coming from the 3 pilot regions (D4.4);
- Factsheet on each training program (D5.1);
- Booklet on the guidelines for small business on how to communicate – 24 EU languages (D5.4);

4.3 Collaboration with other projects and initiatives

As part of our consortium’s effort to optimise our Dissemination and Communication strategy and to maximise the impact, its effects and impacts in the blue bio-based community, and the general public as well, we have been establishing a communication and collaboration system amongst our existing networks and ecosystems (existing partnerships/projects, participation in clusters and relevant associations, etc). Table 10 below presents the list of the already created collaborations.

Table 10: List of the already established collaborations

Project/network name	Brief description
BIOLOC	BIOLOC project is funded by European Commission, and it promotes social innovation and inclusion as enabling factors to accelerate the transition to circular bioeconomy and thus contributes to revitalizing local communities in 12 European regions in Bulgaria, Croatia, the Czech Republic, Germany, Greece, Hungary, Italy, the Netherlands, Romania, Slovakia, Slovenia, and Spain. Through extensive interdisciplinary research and cross-sectoral analyses, BIOLOC will elaborate on concepts and solutions that will trigger positive cascading effects on communities by fostering a participatory and inclusive approach to develop resilient innovative biobased activities open to the contribution of socially disadvantaged or marginalised groups. In this way, it will deliver innovative and inclusive business models and drive the establishment of permanent public-private multistakeholder hubs to pioneer a social dialogue on innovative and inclusive circular bioeconomy as a leveraging factor for sustainable and resilient local communities.

BLUEBIOCLUSTERS	BlueBioClusters overarching objective is to support and increase the uptake of sustainable blue bioeconomy business opportunities by European (coastal) regions, companies, and citizens (incl. low-income populations), to contribute to regional development and the EU Green Deal by improving the services of blue bioeconomy clusters throughout Europe to both public as well as private actors.
BLUE BIO COFUND	The first co-funded call launched 17 December 2018. The COFUND partners have committed EUR 23,5 million, which will make up a maximum total budget of EUR 30 million including up to EUR 6.5 million co-funding from the European Commission. The goal is to identify new and improve existing ways of bringing bio-based products and services to the market and find new ways of creating value from in the blue bioeconomy. Next to the co-funded call, the BlueBio COFUND plans to contribute to the national priorities as well as to the strategic research agenda of JPI Oceans, and the ERA-NETs COFASP and MBT. Participating countries in the BlueBio COFUND are Belgium, Denmark, Estonia, Finland, Germany, Greece, Iceland, Ireland, Italy, Malta, Norway, Portugal, Romania, Spain, and Sweden.
MAIA	The MAIA project connects communities, platforms, knowledge, and research on climate change. The MAIA project aims to function as an impact multiplier of climate research projects funded under the Horizon Europe and Horizon 2020 programmes. The aim of the project is to make the current disperse knowledge more interoperable, accessible, usable, and rendering the outcomes more economically sustainable
SUBMARINER Network for Blue Growth EEIG	The SUBMARINER Network brings together actors from the Baltic Sea Region to actively promote innovative and sustainable uses of marine resources for the dual priorities of protecting our marine ecosystems and promoting sustainable economic development. The Network connects authorities, research institutions, civil society, and private companies, integrating local perspectives into transnational frameworks. As a flagship network under the EU Strategy for the Baltic Sea Region (EUSBSR) and the coordinator of the Horizon CSA Blue Mission BANOS, they represent the blue economy at a trans-regional level. The SUBMARINER Network is a registered not-for-profit European Economic Interest Grouping (EEIG).
THE EUROPEAN BIOECONOMY NETWORK	Initiated by the BIOVOICES project in March 2018 and launched in May, the European Bioeconomy Network (EuBioNet) is a proactive alliance of 47 EU funded projects dealing with Bioeconomy promotion, communication, and

	<p>support. Their main objectives are: i) increase the awareness of environmental, societal and economic benefits of Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy in Europe; ii) stimulate the debate, knowledge sharing and mutual learning to address bioeconomy related challenges and opportunity; iii) identify impact-oriented strategies to boost the sustainable circular bioeconomy in Europe; iv) design a joint and consolidated action plan of communication activities; v) facilitate networking and collaboration between stakeholders; vi) support the MS and regions in developing awareness, communication and education activities on Sustainable Circular Bioeconomy.</p>
--	---

All these projects are present in a dedicated page in our website. We follow and engage their social media channels, strive to continue a strong relationship with these projects and initiatives, and explore opportunities to participate in each other external events.

All consortium is also focused on increasing the initial mapping of complementary EU projects, in particular the ones funded under the HORIZON CL6-2021-COMMUNITIES-01-02: Expertise and training centre on rural innovation is an important component, to further our network and collaboration.

4.4 Updates in the communication of external and internal events

In the first period of the project, it has organised 4 internal events, such as workshops, interviews, and project meetings. In the table below the list of internal events developed so far is presented.

Table 11: List of internal events

Date	Event Title Location	Partners involved	Nr. Participants (approx.)
29-30/09/2022	Project Kick – off Meeting - Rome, Italy -	All	25
16-17/11/2023	Project Meeting - Gothenburg, Sweden	All	25
03/02/2023	Seminar “Blue Bioeconomy in the waters of western Estonia” - Kuressaare, Estonia -	EMU	94
06/07/2023	Seminar “Blue Bioeconomy vision 2035 for Saaremaa Island” - Kõiguste, Saaremaa -	EMU	18

In addition to the workshops that will be organised under the project within WP3 and WP5, the partners are encouraged to participate in events, conferences, and workshops with the purpose of disseminating knowledge of the project activities, create awareness and to communicate the project's findings and results to a wider group of experts or non-experts.

The project partners are encouraged to monitor relevant events and insert their information in the shared document under the spreadsheet "C&D actions" available in the project sharepoint.

For the 1st period the partners have reported the participation in 12 external events, reaching approximately more than 3080 people. The full list of events and number of participants potentially reached in each event is presented in table 12.

Table 12: List of external events

Date	Event Title Location	Partners involved	Nr. Participants (approx.)
22/09/2022	Webinar EU coordinators cluster 6 - Online -	LOBA; APRE	50
05/10/2022	EuBioNet workshop "projects2projects" - Brussels, Belgium -	APRE	70
06-07/10/2022	EU Bioeconomy conference - Brussels, Belgium -	APRE	200
24-25/10/2022	Planetiers World Gathering - Lisbon, Portugal -	LOBA	1200
8/12/2022	BLUESEALAND EXPO - Mazara del Vallo, Italy -	DFBG	40
25/05/2023	Bioeconomy Day - Rome, Italy -	APRE	60
22/10/2023	Maker Faire - Rome, Italy -	APRE	20
29-31/10/2023	Planetiers World Gatherings - Aveiro, Portugal -	LOBA	300
10/11/2023	ECOMUNDO - Rimini, Italy -	APRE	100
14-16/11/2023	1st MISSION ARENA - Gothenberg, Sweden-	APRE	495
29/09/2023	European Researchers night - Palermo, Italy -	UNIPA	500

15/12/2023	Innovative Governance Workshop - Palermo, Italy -	UNIPA	50
------------	--	-------	----

For the 2nd period of the project the following events listed in the table below will be considered:

Table 13: List of potential events

Date	Event Location
20-21/03/2024	EUROPEAN RESEARCH AND INNOVATION DAYS (R&I DAYS) - Brussels, Belgium -
11-14/03/2024	World Ocean Summit - Lisbon, Portugal -
26-27/06/2024	World Bio Markets - The Hague, Netherlands -
04-08/03/2024	European Ocean Days - Brussels, Belgium -
13-14/03/2024	BIOECONOMY CHANGEMAKERS FESTIVAL - Brussels, Belgium -

5 Support Tool

This section provides an overview of the developments of the support tool that enables the BlueRev stakeholders to operate within the project goals of Piloting. The online tool is referred to as the result of the Task 2.3 Support tool (Task leader: LOBA, Partners involved: all) (M1-M36), and its development and function is described as a subchapter in this deliverable due to the link with the Communication Dissemination and Exploitation goals, as well due to LOBA being the developer entity.

This platform is conceptualised to be an Open Space that contains materials developed within the project, including multimedia contents and demonstrative videos for best practices implemented, lessons recordings and related materials, best practices guidelines etc., and standard info i.e. project and partners, calendar of events, news, etc., by facilitating cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the bio-based economy and to provide a knowledge centre to share relevant project results.

The purpose of the Support Tool is to host an online space for mutual exchange, collaboration, communication, and training that will empower the stakeholders to achieve the envisioned results in their communities. Four types of users are expected to frequent the tool and make the best of its use: Company managers (including NGOs, Social enterprises, SMEs, fishery, and biomass sectors, etc), Policy makers, Trainees, and Project partners.

This platform was scheduled to be launched in 4 distinct phases, that have all been completed and integrated online in a fully functional environment:

- **Registration and Profile creation:** the users can register in the platform, create their profile, and choose and customise specific settings. The users will have access to the homepage, calendar where they can create events, and see the upcoming webinars and training courses.
- **Community feed:** this feature allows users to interact with each other, send direct messages, choose discussion topics, and even share documents within the discussion forums.
- **E-library:** an online library where users will be able to access exclusive materials like factsheets, infographics, best practices, multimedia content, and much more.
- **Training courses and webinars:** users will be able to register, attend and download training courses and webinars, both available in live and streaming. Each training course and webinar will allow a discussion forum where the participants may interact with other participants and the lecturer, asking questions, cross-examine facts and share opinions.

The final phase was completed in January 2024 and the platform is now available to all stakeholders, hosted in the URL: <https://support-tool.blurevproject.eu/>. Three guidelines were created to ensure all users can use every feature in a seamless manner. They are available in the footer of the platform as shown in the figure 1. We are also developing video support to complement the guidelines already in place.

Figure 1: Support tool footer

A multi-language option is planned for future implementations. We expect to be able to implement Italian, Estonian and Dutch language options in addition to English which is already implemented.

A help-desk support team is also in place to provide immediate support to questions and doubts users might experience when using the platform. This task will be the responsibility of LOBA who also created the platform. If necessary, a FAQs section will also be implemented in the platform to provide more information to the users.

5.1 Technical sheet for the Support Tool

A technical sheet for a better understanding of the tool was created. This document provides the list of various technologies used and the features we can encounter in the BlueRev Support Tool. It gives an overview of all elements and functionalities on the platform.

5.1.1 Introduction to the platform and the technology used

What is the BlueRev Support Tool?

The BlueRev Support Tool is an online platform built on Moodle technology, in which the BlueRev Project Partners can share information about the project activities and the Blue Economy. The Support Tool is hosted in the URL: <https://support-tool.bluevproject.eu/>

The BlueRev Support Tool offers online courses, webinars, social tools, and a plethora of other information to help participants develop their skills and knowledge about the blue economy, be it technologies, research, applications, and challenges. The BlueRev

Project also fosters collaboration and networking among the participants, the partner institutions, and the industry stakeholders.

The BlueRev's Moodle platform is a web-based learning management system that allows the participants to access the course materials, interact with the instructors and peers, and track their progress and learned experiences. The Moodle platform is a user-friendly and flexible tool that supports the BlueRev Project's vision of creating a community having the Blue Economy at its core.

Why use Moodle?

Moodle, short for Modular Object-Oriented Dynamic Learning Environment, is an open-source learning management system (LMS) designed to facilitate online education and training.

Developed to meet the evolving needs of educators and learners, Moodle provides a versatile platform for creating, delivering, and managing educational content in various formats. With a modular and adaptable architecture, Moodle supports a wide range of features, including course management, content creation, assessments, discussion forums, and collaborative activities. Its user-friendly interface empowers educators, often referred to as "teachers" or "course creators", to design engaging online courses and interact with learners.

Moodle fosters a collaborative learning environment by allowing participants, or "students," to access course materials, submit assignments, and engage in discussions. Its robust set of tools, combined with the flexibility of customization and a supportive community, makes Moodle a popular choice for institutions, organisations, and educators seeking a dynamic online learning experience.

What is a Course?

In Moodle, a course is a space where teachers add learning materials and activities for their students. However, Moodle's flexible architecture allows for the creation and management of a multitude of webpages. The base structure of a course can be built upon for a vast array of functionalities or interactions. As such, a page may be a list of shared documents, a video gallery or even a social forum meant to be used by all users, but still be called a course by Moodle, since it used the course framework as a base.

For the purposes of avoiding ambiguity and any possible confusion, from now on, in this document, any webpage that is not intended as a course, even if it was created upon the course framework, will be referred to as webpage.

5.1.2 Structure and functionalities of the BlueRev Support Tool

User structure and hierarchy

The user structure of the eLearning platform encompasses three distinct roles, each assigned specific responsibilities and privileges. At the pinnacle is the **Administrator**, a

select few who hold the role of general website administrators. This exclusive group manages the overall functioning of the platform, overseeing system configurations, security, and other global settings.

In the role of **Project Partners**, course creators are empowered to design, develop, and administer courses within the platform, share insightful documents and webinars. They hold the key responsibility for content creation, curriculum design, and assessment. All Project Partners need to be validated by one of the administrators.

On the learning side, **Trainees** constitute the end-users actively engaging with educational content. Trainees play a significant role in the platform's dynamic and collaborative learning environment, not only engaging with the training materials, but also sharing and participating with the remaining community by participating in the platform's Social Forum and suggesting new entries for the Get inspired gallery.

This three-tiered user structure ensures a clear delineation of roles, providing the necessary permissions for efficient administration, content creation, and learning experiences within the eLearning platform.

There are, however, other types of users, that can be attributed upon account creation or changed upon request. These are the Company Manager, Policy Maker and a generalised Other. These types are possible using the Cohorts functionality available in the Moodle platform. These user types share, ultimately, the same permission sets as the Trainee group, but can be leveraged by Project Partners and administrators (upon request) for a multitude of uses, such as restricting courses, sending emails and enabling Moodle functionalities only to certain groups of users.

Partner Courses

The course functionality within Moodle forms the backbone of the eLearning platform, providing a robust and versatile framework for the creation, management, and delivery of educational content.

Partner Courses are seamlessly organised, allowing Project Partners to design structured learning paths with diverse resources such as text, multimedia, questionnaires, and other interactive activities. The modular architecture facilitates easy updates and modifications to course content, ensuring adaptability to evolving educational needs. Moodle's intuitive interface empowers educators to set course parameters, personalised to each of the Project Partner's preferences.

The platform's flexibility accommodates various course formats, from self-paced to instructor-led, fostering a personalised learning experience. Integrated communication tools, such as forums and messaging, enhance interaction between Project Partners and Trainees. The courses functionality in Moodle not only simplifies content creation but also prioritises user engagement and effective learning outcomes, making it a comprehensive and user-friendly solution for online education.

For the sake of project focus and streamlining the eLearning experience, certain course resources and activities have been intentionally omitted from the current configuration of the Moodle platform. However, it is important to note that Moodle's inherent flexibility allows for the seamless addition of these removed elements should the project requirements evolve or expand in the future. The modular nature of Moodle's architecture ensures that features like interactive multimedia, wikis, assignments, or additional resource types can be effortlessly reintegrated to meet changing instructional needs.

This deliberate design decision was made to optimise the current learning environment, but also anticipates the potential for future enhancements or customizations, providing a scalable and adaptable platform that can easily evolve with the evolving demands of the educational initiatives.

Webinars

The eLearning platform features a dedicated Webinars page, leveraging Moodle's database activity. This page serves as a dynamic hub for Project Partners to enhance the learning experience by curating YouTube videos as webinars. The flexibility of the platform allows Project Partners to seamlessly add any YouTube video to the list, along with associated relevant information, learning resources in the form of informative webinars, talks and other videos for Trainees.

In instances where Project Partners wish to incorporate a webinar not available on YouTube, a streamlined process has been established. Project Partners can reach out to the Support Tool's Support Team or Administrators, who are readily available to assist. Upon request, the administrators facilitate the integration by uploading the video to YouTube and making the video unlisted, ensuring seamless and secure integration into the platform, while keeping it exclusive to members within the BlueRev community, if so desired.

The fields within the webinar database entries have been designed to be highly flexible, allowing Project Partners to adapt and customise them based on their specific instructional needs. These fields can be easily modified to accommodate varying types of webinar content and associated information. This flexibility empowers Project Partners to tailor the entry fields to align with the unique requirements of each webinar, ensuring a dynamic and adaptable structure that enhances the platform's capacity to cater to diverse learning scenarios. The user-friendly interface facilitates quick adjustments, providing Project Partners with the autonomy to optimise the webinar database to best suit the evolving content and pedagogical goals of their courses.

Documents

The platform includes a Documents database, offering Project Partners a dedicated space to share and disseminate several types of critical materials such as important findings, research papers, and other relevant document types supported by the Moodle platform. This feature enhances collaboration and knowledge sharing among Project Partners of different institutions, fostering a centralised repository for valuable resources.

The Documents database is designed to support a variety of document formats, ensuring flexibility and compatibility with several types of content. Project Partners can easily add entries through simple forms, ensuring an accessible and simple usage in sharing these resources to all the users in the platform.

Much like the Webinar database, the fields that are available in each of the entries can be changed upon request, given the need for new relevant information.

Get inspired

The Get Inspired database is a collaborative feature on the platform, functioning similarly to the Documents database but with broader user participation. Users across the platform, including Trainees, have the ability to contribute entries containing documents, images (displayed through a small gallery), and useful links. However, to ensure the quality and relevance of the shared content, these entries require validation from either a Project Partner or an Administrator. This validation process ensures that the materials align with the educational objectives and standards set by the Project Partners, maintaining the integrity and reliability of the Get Inspired database. By allowing diverse contributions from all users while maintaining oversight through validation, this feature encourages a collaborative and dynamic environment where valuable resources and inspirations can be shared and accessed by the entire learning community.

Much like the Webinar and Document databases, the fields that are available in each of the entries can be changed upon request, given the need for new relevant information.

Community

The Social Feed page serves as a centralised site-wide forum, fostering community engagement and interaction within the eLearning platform. Functioning as a standard forum, users, including both Project Partners and Trainees, have the ability to create new threads, initiate discussions, and interact with each other. This functionality makes use of the Open Forum plugin, which ensures a more flexible forum experience when compared to the one already available through Moodle. The platform encourages dynamic communication by allowing users to share not only text-based messages but also multimedia files, enhancing the richness and diversity of content exchanged. This Social Feed creates a virtual space for collaborative learning, enabling users to ask questions, share insights, and engage in discussions that extend beyond the specific course structures. By providing a versatile and accessible forum for communication, the Social Feed contributes to building a sense of community among platform users, fostering a collaborative and supportive learning environment.

6 Update Exploitation and Sustainability Initial Guidelines

6.1 Introduction

This part of the document entails the BlueRev Exploitation guidelines that aim to kick-start the formulation of the related strategy and set the foreground for the creation of the Final Exploitation and Replication Plan (D6.3), due in M36. Thus, it provides an initial introduction to the definitions that the partnership commonly understands, as well as some first tools that partners will use to conceptualize their actions. This plan reinforces important terms that are related to the project success during and after its end, referring mainly to the Exploitation, and tightly driven by the need for Valorisation and Sustainability that will come as a result of a well-designed strategy and implemented actions. During the project course, one more related deliverable will be utilized to set the stage for an even more successful Exploitation, Valorisation and Sustainability, namely referring to:

“Final Exploitation and replication plan” (D6.3, M36) This deliverable at the end of the project will be the most important document to ensure the viability of the work done, and thus a great level of commitment will be drawn from the partnership for its successful implementation beyond the funding period.

6.2 Adopted definitions

6.2.1 Exploitation

Exploitation is associated with the use of the project's results at different levels, during and after the implementation of the project. It is related to the necessary action that will bring visibility to the project in order to involve the target groups, end-users, stakeholders and transfer the results/products into their professionals' scope. Exploitation is mostly related to the idea of convincing the key actors to use the main products of a project. Exploitation is strongly associated with the sustainability of the project after its conclusion since exploitation activities should ensure that the results of the project are used by its target groups and possibly are transferred to other contexts (e.g. other countries; other pedagogical areas, other sectors).

The exploitation is split into two components: mainstreaming and multiplication. Mainstreaming means to address the decision-makers in order to convince them to introduce/take into account the results/products of a project, while multiplication is more focused on persuading individual end-users to adopt those products. This usage can be within the partnership and outside, at the local, regional, national, or European level. As in the case of dissemination, the exploitation process should be planned and organised

at the beginning of the project by a methodological document (e.g. Exploitation Strategy) that orientates the whole consortium.

6.2.2 Valorisation

Valorisation is a term that includes dissemination and exploitation, and it aims to make the project result/product more valuable to everybody, meaning make “others” use the product. Valorisation is the sum of both dissemination and exploitation activities. The overall objective of valorisation activities is to promote the project and its results and foster their use by different individuals and organisations, with the attempt to constantly spread and improve the usage and the content of the results. Valorisation involves not only the testing and dissemination of the results of the most innovative projects but also the exploitation of these results and their development in new contexts and environments. It includes the sustainable application of these results over time in formal and informal systems, in the practices of organisations as well as in the personal learning goals of every individual. The two main benefits of valorisation are the return enhancement on public and private investments in the area of training/education as well as innovation in training and educational systems. These benefits easily explain why it is recognised as a clear and increased political importance of valorisation in Europe. Valorisation means planning in such a way that the resources affected to a project generate results that can be used and exploited on a large scale, with the view of benefiting as many individuals and organisations as possible. Valorisation must be based on a meticulous ex-ante analysis of needs to be fulfilled by a project as well as on a clear identification of the results expected and this from the right beginning. Effective valorisation requires the active involvement, at the project design stage, of the potential users and target groups who are to benefit from the project and who are ultimately expected to exploit the results.

6.2.3 Sustainability

Sustainability is the capacity of the project to continue its existence and functioning beyond its end. The project results are used and exploited continuously. Sustainability of results implies the use and exploitation of results in the long term. A project can be considered as sustainable if its outcomes continue after the end of EU funding. As the sustainability of project outcomes may be difficult to anticipate and to describe – most are not tangible, this Initial Plan focuses on the sustainability of products and results. Sustainability may not concern all the aspects of a project. In each project, some results may be maintained, while others may not be so necessary to maintain. A project can, therefore, be considered as sustainable if relevant results are pursued and products are maintained or developed after the end of the EU funding (i.e. duration of new courses, updating of new tools). It is not easy to achieve a plan in order to generate the desired sustainability of the project and somehow ensure a return on investment at European level by multiplying the benefits that the assimilation of best practices can provide. Hence, this is often one of the project weaknesses, and simultaneously one aspect that EU values most.

6.3 Purpose of the Exploitation guidelines

The BlueRev Exploitation guidelines set the ground to start the formulation of a strategy towards clearly described aims and objectives, defined targeted groups, tools for mainstreaming and upscaling the results as well as action plans that will guarantee the Valorisation, Multiplication and Sustainability of the project.

The exploitation strategy will be in line with the needs of the fulfilment of the contractual expectations that respond to:

- European Commission's (EC) requirement to communicate the consortium's strategy and report on planned exploitation activities.
- Consortium partners need to inform about participants' required activities and responsibilities concerning the exploitation of the results after the project ends.

According to the Mainstreaming and Multiplication terms defined by the EU, and adopted within the BlueRev project proposal, the exploitation strategy, and its implementation within else will be also unfolded on two fronts:

- On the one hand, activities targeting the involvement of decision-makers at the political level in order to ensure mainstreaming of the project results.
- On the other hand, activities will be targeted at spreading project results among end-users and at promoting their use, satisfying the multiplication perspective.

For the above to succeed, the project coordinator and all the partners and key actors need to embrace exploitation as a process that reaches beyond the life of the project so that its results are sustained:

“The goal of the exploitation strategy and its implementation plan is, therefore, to explain how during and after the end of the project the results will be exploited to make them sustainable.”

The exploitation plan sets out the activities related to and facilitating, the exploitation of the results by the end and/or potential users and for the benefit of target groups clearly identified from the project design stage. To achieve these goals during the implementation, it elaborates the following issues:

- Define clearly and keep on identifying the target groups/end users/public and political stakeholders of the project's results;
- Ensure that these identified target groups/end users/public and political stakeholders will be involved during the lifetime of the project;
- Clarify how, during and after the end of the project, the results will be exploited and sustained;
- Guarantee that the project results are available and visible after project conclusion;
- Ensure that the network created by the project is enriched sustainably;
- Ensure that the transfer of knowledge and good practices are set up.

Moreover, the initial Exploitation Plan provides an overview of the BlueRev activities and results. It aims to be used as a guide to all partners to highlight the details on partners' activities and responsibilities after the official date of the end of the project. The specific objectives of the Exploitation activities are:

- To promote and raise awareness about the project contents, developments, and results;
- To successfully transfer the results to appropriate decision-makers to achieve their sustainable promotion and support;
- To convince end-users to adopt and/or apply the results, also after the project and support by its partnership has ended.

6.4 Target audiences

Figure 2: BlueRev target groups clustering

The target audiences are defined and approached under the two different perspectives, for Mainstreaming the results and Multiplication. According to this, the first group described below, as closer to the policymaking, is to be approached with a mindset and actions that foster the Mainstreaming of the BlueRev results:

- National authorities
- Regional authorities
- Local authorities

Moreover, BlueRev partners will pursue the use of the results by the following target groups that will be encouraged to adopt the innovations that were introduced by the BlueRev project and thus satisfy the multiplication needs:

- Knowledge providers
- Scientific communities
- Community knowledge
- Associations
- Cooperatives

- Regional clusters
- Civil Society Organizations
- NGOs
- Marginalized groups
- SMEs
- Primary Biomass Producers

6.5 IPR Management Strategy

Under the frame of BlueRev and for the aforementioned strategic targets of Exploitation, Sustainability and Valorization of the project methodology and results, key IP and innovation management will be employed, with a view to setting a common understanding concerning the background, foreground, ownership (including joint ownership), access and usage rights, dissemination and exploitation during and after the project development. In this respect, the BlueRev IPR management strategy will apply a comprehensive framework which will separate the IP management processes of the project in the following stages:

- Grant Agreement preparation stage
- Project implementation stage
- Post-project stage

In this respect, the following figure illustrates the IPR management stages, as will be considered and followed within BlueRev. More details about these stages will be developed in later timing of the implementation and in the following deliverables.

Figure 3: The BlueRev stages of IPR definition and implementation

6.5.1 Definitions

Background IP: Background IP can be **defined as data, know-how or information – including any rights - owned or licensed to a project partner prior to the commencement of the agreement and needed to implement the action or exploit the project’s assets.** The background needed for carrying out the project activities or exploiting the underlying results must be accessible to the other project partners **on a royalty-free basis.** Under this frame, all project partners must identify the background as pertinent for the project actions and grant access rights to this IP¹. The background of a project can be identified and agreed:

- (i) Within the consortium agreement, after the internal evaluation of pre-existing knowledge, or
- (ii) in a separate agreement (“agreement on the background”).

In this respect, there are two main aspects to consider when dealing with the background of a project²:

- **Identification of background:** Naming of the assets that each project partner provides to the consortium, and which are imperative for the successful implementation and exploitation of the project actions.
- **Definition of Access Rights:** Clarification of the rights to use knowledge under the terms and conditions agreed within the consortium and align with the underlying background rules and obligations set by the EC in order to ensure the smooth implementation of the project.

Foreground IP: Foreground refers to **the results and assets that are generated through the implementation of project activities**, including pieces of information, materials, and knowledge³. These results comprise any tangible or intangible output of the project’s actions which can be protectable or not. In this respect, foreground IP can arise and be obtained from project partners in order to protect and exploit the underlying exploitable results of the project. It includes intellectual property rights (e.g. copyrights, industrial designs, patents), similar forms of protection (e.g. rights for databases) and unprotected know-how (e.g. confidential material). It should be noted that results generated outside the project activities cannot be defined as foreground.

BlueRev’s Consortium Agreement establishes that results of the project are owned by the project partner who generates them⁴. Given the collaborative nature of the project,

¹ See Consortium Agreement for a detailed description of the background and the access rights granted

² European Commission, European Innovation Council and SMEs Executive Agency, Scherer, J., Weber, S., Alveen, P., et al., *European IP Helpdesk: successful valorisation of knowledge and research results in Horizon Europe : boosting the impact of your project through effective communication, dissemination and exploitation*, Publications Office of the European Union, 2022, Available at: <https://data.europa.eu/doi/10.2826/437645>.

³ For a detailed definition of the Foreground see: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/glossary/foreground>.

⁴ Par 8.1: Ownership of Results

some results can be jointly developed by several partners⁵. In this case, **joint ownership can arise among the contributing partners and is subject to the agreement on the allocation and terms of the exercise of their joint ownership**. Although regulations concerning the frame of joint ownership are embedded in the BlueRev Consortium Agreement, it would be best practice for partners to establish during the project implementation a separate joint ownership agreement in order to define the allocation and terms of exercising their ownership. Each joint owner can grant non-exclusive licenses to third parties to exploit the joint-owned results unless otherwise agreed in the CA or the joint ownership agreement.

Exploitable Results: Exploitation of project's results means the utilization of results in further research activities other than those covered by the action concerned (e.g. in other research activities; or in developing, creating, and marketing a product or process; or in creating and providing a service, or in standardization activities)⁶. Under this scheme, an **exploitable result** is defined as a project result (expected or achieved) that meets the following two conditions:

- Has commercial/social/academic relevance.
- Can be commercialized/exploited as a standalone result (e.g. product, process, service, etc. A patent for licensing is also an exploitable result.).

Therefore, exploitable results can be a combination or part of a foreground result(s). Not all foreground items may meet the above conditions⁷. Furthermore, exploitable results are not necessarily market ready; they may require further R&D, engineering, and validation before becoming commercially exploitable.

Access Rights: Access rights refer to one partner's rights for requesting access to another project partner's background and foreground to implement its activities under the project or to use its own results. Additionally, access rights can be used as long as they are needed for exploiting the project's results. The provisions governing access rights within a collaborative Horizon Europe project follow specific rules pre-defined in the Grant Agreement and the Consortium Agreement. Access rights within BlueRev are presented in the table below:

Table 14: Access Rights

Purpose of access	Access to Background	Access to Results
Project implementation	Royalty free Unless otherwise agreed by participants	Royalty free

⁵ Par 8.2: Joint ownership

⁶ European Commission, Glossary, Available at: <https://ec.europa.eu/info/funding-tenders/opportunities/portal/screen/support/glossary>

⁷ European Commission, Communication, Dissemination And Exploitation Why They All Matter And What Is The Difference?, Available at: https://ec.europa.eu/research/participants/docs/h2020-funding-guide/imgs/quick-guide_diss-expl_en.pdf,

Exploitation of Own results	<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Subject on individual agreement• Granted under fair and reasonable conditions
-----------------------------	--

Protection of Results: It should be noted that when considering IP protection, IP assets can be protected by several types of IPR, and therefore, the most appropriate protection strategy must be chosen. The selection of the most suitable form of IP protection depends on the nature and specific characteristics of the results under consideration and the objectives of the IP owner. There are various types of instruments that may be considered for protecting IP. Under the frame of BlueRev, meaningful IP protection instruments that can be used are the following:

- Trade and service marks;
- Patents;
- Utility models;
- Copyrights;
- Trade secrets;
- Confidentiality agreements.

Further details about each of the above-mentioned protection instruments are provided in the subsections below.

- **Trade Marks:**

A trademark constitutes an exclusive right over the use of a sign in relation to the goods and services for which it is registered⁸. Trademarks consist of signs capable of distinguishing the products (either goods or services) of a trader from those of others. The main function of a trademark is to identify the commercial origin of a product. This does not mean that it should inform the consumer of the actual person who has manufactured the product or even the one who is trading in it. It is sufficient that consumers can trust in a given enterprise, not necessarily known to them, being responsible for the product sold under the trademark.

- **Service Marks:**

In modern trade, consumers are confronted not only with a vast choice of goods of all kinds but also with an increasing variety of services which tend more and more to be offered on a national and international scale. There is therefore a need for signs that enable consumers to distinguish between different services such as insurance companies, car rental firms, airlines, etc. These signs are called service marks and fulfil essentially the same origin-indicating and distinguishing function for services as trademarks do for goods. Since service marks are signs which are very similar in nature to trademarks, the same criteria could be applied. Thus, service mark protection has sometimes been introduced by a very short amendment to the existing trademark law or

⁸ For the definition of trademark in Europe, see: <https://iprhelpdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>,

simply by providing for protection of service marks under of the provisions of the trademark law⁹.

- **Patents:**

A patent is an exclusive right granted for the protection of inventions (products or processes) that offers a new technical solution or facilitates a new way of doing something. The patent holder has the exclusive right to prevent third parties from commercially exploiting their invention for a limited period. In return, the patent holder must disclose the invention to the public in the patent application¹⁰. Patent owner has the right to decide who may or may not use the patented invention throughout the period during which the invention is protected. Additionally, the patent owner may give permission to other parties, or permit them, to use the invention on mutually agreed terms. The owner may also sell the right to the invention to someone, who then becomes the new owner of the patent. Finally, patents are granted only country by country, some regionally (e.g. European), and may also be used in non-patented territories (although in such case they would not enjoy patent protection). Once a patent expires, the protection ends, and the invention becomes part of the public domain, meaning that owners do not hold exclusive rights any longer. Therefore, it becomes available for commercial exploitation, free of charge, by others¹¹.

- **Utility Models:**

Also referred to as a “petty patent”, a utility model is an exclusive right granted for an invention, which allows its owner to prevent others from commercially using the protected invention, without their authorization, for a limited period¹². The inclusion of utility models into the intellectual property system in some countries has the primary objective of nurturing the rapid evolution of indigenous innovativeness, particularly in small and medium-sized enterprises and among individuals¹³.

- **Copyrights:**

Copyright (or author’s right) is the term used to describe the economic and moral rights that creators have over their literary, scientific, and artistic works. It is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original¹⁴. There

⁹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law, and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 68f

¹⁰ Definition of patents in the European context retrieved from:

<https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>, .

¹¹ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 17

¹² Definition of utility models in the European context retrieved from:

<https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>,

¹³ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40

¹⁴ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40

is not an exhaustive list containing the works that can be protected by copyright. However, there are several works usually covered by copyright at an international level¹⁵:

- Literary works such as novels, poems, plays, newspaper articles;
- Computer programs, databases;
- Films, musical compositions, and choreographies;
- Artistic works such as paintings, drawings, etc.;
- Advertisements, maps, and technical drawings.

Copyright protection also includes moral rights, including the right to claim authorship of a work, and the right to oppose changes to it that could harm the creator's reputation. The creator - or the owner of the copyright in a work - can enforce rights administratively and in the courts, by inspection of premises for evidence of production or possession of illegally made “pirated” goods related to protecting works. The owner may obtain court orders to stop such activities, as well as seek damages for loss of financial rewards and recognition. Finally, it is important to note that copyright only protects the expression of ideas represented in a physical embodiment, not the ideas themselves, and provided the expression is original¹⁶.

- **Trade Secrets:**

Any confidential business information that provides a competitive advantage to an enterprise can be considered a trade secret. The type of information that could be protected as a trade secret is therefore highly diverse. It could include know-how, technical knowledge (potentially protectable as a patent), but also business and commercial data such as lists of customers, business plans, recipes, or manufacturing processes¹⁷.

- **Confidentiality Agreements:**

Confidentiality is an extremely prominent issue for participants in innovation projects, from the setting-up stage to the implementation and exploitation phases. BlueRev is a CSA project, so this kind of agreement should not be critical. Exchanging valuable information with other partners is generally a necessity that regularly occurs in collaborative initiatives or undertakings. Accordingly, confidentiality issues and measures should be taken into consideration to safely exchange information, facilitate the project development and ensure the non-disclosure of sensitive technology, business, or commercially confidential information. Confidentiality agreements provide protection and security to an organization that is about to share or make available information to another organization by ensuring that confidential information will be used only for the permitted purposes agreed between the signatories of the agreement and

¹⁵ Definition of copyrights in the European context retrieved from

<https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>,

¹⁶ See WIPO Intellectual Property Handbook 2008: Policy, Law and Use. Chapter 2: Fields of Intellectual Property Protection, p. 40.

¹⁷ Definition of trade secrets in the European context retrieved from

<https://iprhelppdesk.eu/sites/default/files/2018-12/european-ipr-helpdesk-your-guide-to-ip-in-europe.pdf>

will not be used or revealed to third parties without consent. Therefore, the signature of a confidentiality agreement could be an especially important step to keep confidential information secret in order to maintain a competitive edge¹⁸. There are specific criteria to determine a confidentiality agreement as legally enforceable: i) The information must be secret, i.e. not readily accessible to people that normally deal with this kind of information; ii) It must have commercial value; iii) The owner must have taken reasonable steps to protect it.

6.6 IPR Approach during the Implementation Stage

During the implementation stage of BlueRev, IP handling procedures are foreseen to be applied among the partners to organise the results/assets management of the project. As the project continues, the focus will be on foreground identification, assets' ownership, access rights, and protection, as well as on the exploitation and commercialisation of the project's results. The BlueRev IPR management emphasises on establishing robust handling procedures of the IPR issues that are of strategic importance to the project to facilitate the exploitation of its results. Therefore, partners should focus on two different points:

- Providing access rights to their knowledge for other partners to carry out their work on the project.
- Establishing early asset identification procedures to protect, disseminate and exploit the project's assets.

In this respect, key IP related issues in the BlueRev implementation phase include:

- **Background Identification**

During the first stages of BlueRev is vital to identify the relevant knowledge, know-how and partners' data, which constitute the background of the project. Under this framework, the underlying background could be attached to the generated assets of the project, which, eventually, will help the determination of access rights, ownership issues and IPR.

- **Foreground Identification**

A core process of the BlueRev IP management is the project assets' identification to create a concrete mapping of the projects' assets and enhance the BlueRev IP portfolio. Therefore, all IP valuable assets within the project must be identified, listed, named, described, and analyzed in a systematic way.

- **Results' ownership**

¹⁸ See confidentiality agreements on the WIPO website:
https://www.wipo.int/sme/en/documents/disclosing_inf_fulltext.html

Partners have been asked (through the BlueRev IPR Matrix) to elaborate further on the provisions of the Consortium Agreement regarding the results' ownership. Special attention will be paid on **handling joint ownership issues**.

- **Protection of results**

Effective exploitation of the innovative concepts and assets developed under the frame of BlueRev depends on the protection of the project's results. In particular, the project's results must adequately be protected if¹⁹: i) The project's results can reasonably be expected to be commercially exploited and ii) Protecting them is possible, reasonable and justified (given the circumstances).

On this note, when considering IP protection, BlueRev partners must consider their own interests along with the interests of the consortium. Project partners should safeguard the identified exploitable BlueRev results with adequate protection schemes, which will offer protection period within a suitable geographical territory. The geographical territory should be agreed by the parties in advance, based on where the IP will be used. By default, Europe is considered to be the suitable territory in which the identified exploitable BlueRev results will be safeguarded, but it remains at the discretion of the interested parties to collectively reach an agreement regarding this matter.

The table that follows, illustrates an indicative list of different protection instruments. Considering the CSA nature of the BlueRev project, it is not expected to employ all the instruments in the list. Furthermore, additional protection instruments can be used when deemed suitable as the project activities progress.

Table 15: Indicative list of protection instruments

Subject Matter	Patent	Utility	Copyright	Trademark	Confidential Information
Invention	X	X			X
Software ²⁰	X	X	X		X
Scientific Article			X		
Technology Design			X	X	
Name of Technology				X	
Know How	X	X			X
Website			X	X	X

¹⁹ See: <https://cms.eurice.eu/storage/uploads/news/files/lp-management-in-collab-horizon-projects.pdf>

²⁰ Software patentability is still a debated issue given its exclusion as subject matter as by Article 52(2)(c) and (3) of the European Patent Convention (EPC). Source: IPR Helpdesk

IP protection constitutes a tool to create value through the licensing, sale, or commercialization of IP in the form of products and services. IP utilization is vital for a prospective commercial or industrial exploitation as it could contribute to support the branding of products and services both to customers and investors. It should be noted that the IP protection of an asset is not always mandatory.

- **Exploitation of results**

The identified exploitable results and assets of BlueRev will be effectively exploited for commercial or any other relevant use as foreseen during the BlueRev project. In particular, the BlueRev consortium will seek exploitation opportunities of the project's results in:

- i) Further research activities;
- ii) Developing, creating or marketing a product or process;
- iii) Creating and providing a service;
- iv) Using them in standardisation activities.

- **Dissemination of results**

BlueRev partners are set to select the appropriate means for the dissemination of the project's results (e.g. scientific publications, publication on web sites, conferences, open access, etc.), based on the conditions set forth in the CA and in other specific confidentiality agreements. All partners should be aware that they should first ensure the protection of a project's exploitable result and then proceed to dissemination actions of the underlying result.

6.7 IPR Conflicts

In order to proactively avoid IP conflicts, project partners will be well-informed about IP rules and guided through the exploitation process not only by the IPR Matrix, but also by the coordinator. In this respect, project partners will identify their IPR assets, formulate their ownership and exploitation claims and if deemed necessary, transfer any relevant results to BlueRev exploitable results according to the principal rights and obligations defined in the CA of the project.

The coordinator will help with the following indicative (and not exclusive) issues:

- Is there a possible misunderstanding about the definition of the exploitable result and therefore of the object of claims?
- Are there exploitation claims that should be further specified so that the partners can check the compatibility of their claims?
- Are the foreseen exploitation claims compatible with the ownership claims of the partners (related issue of access rights)?

- Are there any confidentiality issues e.g. on new knowledge of strategic importance for a partner and consequently the need for a confidential agreement?
- Are there any possible IP conflicts between the partners, both related to ownership and the related need for access rights and to exploitation claims?

In case of IP conflict, the coordinator will encourage conflicting parties to get in contact and pro-actively find solutions and sign written agreements whenever necessary. In case no agreement is achieved, an internal mediation process will be kicked off following the provisions of the BlueRev's CA. In case the IP issues remain unresolved after this first mediation procedure, a further mediation process in accordance with the WIPO Mediation Rules will be applied.

6.8 IPR Matrix Methodology

The BlueRev IPR management approach foresees the utilization of an IPR Matrix to define the main IPR issues concerning the BlueRev Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This approach will be supported by all project partners in identifying and managing the background, foreground knowledge and exploitable results of the project, and of potential co-innovators, to have a full overview of IP protection and necessary agreements to enable successful exploitation of the project's offerings. The IPR Matrix methodology will be comprised of 4 distinct but interconnected steps, as follows:

- **Step 1:** Identification of the background IP and definition of access rights among partners within the project.
- **Step 2:** Identification of the assets and results, which constitute the foreground IP of the project and are generated under the BlueRev activities.
- **Step 3:** Identification of the project's exploitable results/assets and the corresponding interest for their further exploitation along with the contributing partners to each result.
- **Step 4:** Definition of a framework of IPR protection for the identified BlueRev assets, to enhance their further exploitation.

Under this framework, the structure of the IPR Matrix that will be used throughout the duration of the project is summarised in the following table:

Table 16: Structure of the IPR Matrix

Background (BG)	Foreground (FG)	Exploitable results (ER)
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Background Number • Relevant Background • Contributing Partner (Partner Name) • Short Description of BG 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Foreground Number • Work Package • Short Description of FG • Specific Project Result as deliverable 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ER number • Exploitable Result (ER) • Short Description Main Partner(s) • Contributing Partners

<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Type of Protection (patent, copyright, ...) How will it be utilized within BlueRev? Conditions to Use within BlueRev? Conditions to use outside BlueRev Interest in further exploitation through BlueRev results 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Main Contributing Partner Further Contributing Partner(s) Related Background Number Type of Protection Conditions to Use within BlueRev Interest in Further Commercialization of BlueRev Results Conditions to Use after the end of the Project 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> FG number (related) BG number (related) Proposition for ER - Owner (if any) Relevance for IP protection (if any) M - Making them and selling them U - Using them L - Licence them S - Providing as a Service O - Others Most promising path Further Comments
--	---	--

6.8.1 Identification of Background IP

During the first stage of the IPR the Background to be used for the project implementation were identified. Multiple information regarding the Background IP is recorded in the respective template (Table 17).

Table 17: IPR Matrix Background Template

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9
Background Number	Relevant Background	Contributing Partner (Partner Name)	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection	How will it be utilized within BlueRev?	Conditions to Use within BlueRev?	Conditions to use outside BlueRev	Interest in further exploitation through BlueRev results

In details:

1st column: the number of the Background for a quick reference.

2nd column: a short name of the Background is given.

3rd column: the partner related to this Background is mentioned.

4th column: a short, but more detailed description of the Background is offered.

5th column: the partners define the type of protection in terms of patents, utility models, copyrights, trade and service marks, trade secrets, creative commons licenses, confidentiality agreements, among others.

6th column: the partners define how this Background will be used in the framework of the project.

7th column: the conditions under which the consortium partners can use the Background (for example: free to use, license fee, restrictions, NDA).

8th column: the conditions under which the stakeholders outside the consortium can use the Background (for example: Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?).

9th column: the partners should state their interest for further exploitation of the Background in the framework of the project through the produced results.

6.8.2 Identification of Foreground IP

In the second stage of the population of the IPR Matrix (Table 18), the partners should identify the Foreground that will be produced during the project’s activities. The Foreground (FG) is a Project Results, including information, being protectable or not, which are generated under the project; belongs to the beneficiary generating it. Can be jointly generated (joint ownership) and can be transferred (third parties).

Table 18: IPR Matrix Foreground Template

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11
Foregr ound Numbe r	Work Pack age	Short Descri ption of FG	Specifi c Project Result as deliver able	Main Contrib uting Partner	Further Contrib uting Partner (s)	Related Backgr ound Number	Type of Protec tion	Condi tions to Use within BlueR ev	Interest in Further Commercial ization of BlueRev Results	Condi tions to Use after the end of the Project

The above template is used by the consortium partners to identify the foreground IP. The BlueRev project achievements are listed along with the respective WP. Then, the main contributing partner is mentioned. Usually, if an FG comes as a direct result of a Task, then the main partner is the Task leader. In addition, the rest of the contributing partners are also mentioned. Similarly, the contributing partners are usually the partners contributing to the Task that the FG emerges from. In details:

1st column: a Foreground number (FG) is assigned (first number refers to WP relevance, second number refers to FG order).

2nd column: the related WP.

3rd column: a short description of the FG.

4th column: the results as deliverable (if any).

5th column: the main responsible partner.

6th column: the contributing partner(s).

7th column: the number of the related Background IP is mentioned.

8th column: similarly to the background identification template, the partners define the type of protection.

9th column: if required, the conditions under which the FG can be used by the consortium partners (i.e.: patent, copyright).

10th column: the interest for the commercialization through the project results.

11th column: the conditions to use after the end of the project shall be indicated by the project partners (e.g., free to use, license fee, etc.).

6.8.3 Identification of Exploitable results

In the third stage of the population of the IPR matrix, and based on the identified FG, the consortium partners will define the exploitable results and the IPR management procedures:

- i) Protection
- ii) Definition of access rights
- iii) Exploitation pathways

The main aim of this third stage of the IPR Matrix is:

- To identify IP ownership and exploitation claims, as well as pro-actively indicate conflicts for each exploitable result; and
- To support decisions on issues pertaining to IP protection, to timely make the needed steps in this regard, including any potential IP agreements (e.g. for joint ownership, providing access rights or even an NDA for confidentiality).

The next table (Table 19) will be used throughout the whole duration of the project to deploy the third stage of the IPR Matrix and identify the exploitable results.

Not all the project results are exploitable results, as for the following definition "Exploitable Results (ER): "Direct or indirect utilization of foreground in further research

activities (other than those covered by the project) or for developing, creating, and marketing a product, a process, or a service. An exploitable result is defined as an outcome of the project (achieved or expected) that meets two conditions:

- (i) It has commercial/social/academic relevance
- (ii) It can be commercialized/exploited as a standalone result (product, process, service, etc.) (a patent for licensing is also an exploitable result)

These results might need further R&D, prototyping, engineering, validation, etc. at the end of the project – before they become commercially exploitable. Exploitable results are generally defined as products, processes, services, methods, etc., which are new, improved or more efficient."

Table 19: IPR Matrix Exploitable Results Template

1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8	9	10	11	12	13	14	15	16
ER number	Exploitable Result (ER)	Short Description	Main Partner(s)	Contributing Partners	FG number (related)	BG number (related)	Proposition for ER - Owner (if any)	Relevance for IP protection (if any)	M - Making the m and selling the m	U - Using the m	L - Licencing the m	S - Providing as a Service	O - Others	Most promising path	Further Comments

Table 19 in details:

1st column: a ER number.

2nd column: a short name of the ER.

3rd column: a short description of the ER.

4th column: the main responsible partner.

5th column: the other contributing partner(s).

6th column: the number of the related FG.

7th column: the number of the related BG required to reach the ER.

8th column: the proposed owner of the exploitable result.

9th column: the relevance for IP protection indicated by the responsible partner.

10th -14th column: to indicate several distinct categories of the exploitation claims.

M: Making a product and selling it.

U: Using the project result internally for further development, for instance:

- To develop something else for sale; or
- For R&D departments (public or private) to use the results in new research projects.

L: Licensing the project result to third parties.

S: Providing a Service, such as consultancy, etc.

O: Others

The partner responsible for the exploitable results with the support of the contributing partners, the coordinator and the exploitation manager shall choose which exploitation claims best fit the ER.

15th column: the most promising exploitation claim shall be indicated.

16th column: further comments can be given.

6.9 IPR Matrix identified

Appendix L presents the IPR Matrix identified as defined by the consortium partners at month 18. Additional modifications are expected in the updated version of the Exploitation and Sustainability Plan, which will correspond to the progress of the project and the produced results and knowhow.

6.10 Re-cap of the BlueRev promo-toolkit

A wide set of tools will be used by the partnership to support the mainstreaming and multiplying of the main results of the project, within these tools having the:

Figure 4: CDE schematic

6.10.1 Website & Support tool

The project's window for the community is the website - <https://www.blurevproject.eu/> , and the tool for its upscaling is the Support Tool that will be developed in a subdomain and will be open access to the consortium members and the public.

The website serves as a presentation of the project, its aims and objectives, materials, and consortium members.

The Support Tool is the tool for implementing the Piloting and supports the participants in their journey.

LOBA will assume the maintenance of the website and the Support Tool for at least 5 years after the end of the project.

Additionally, the project coordinator and partners' contacts will be available in both platforms in case a potential user needs further information about the project.

6.10.2 Social media networks

The social media are populated with online “alive” activity and show that BlueRev is not only contributing to the sector but also staying up to date with the news.

The social media pages ([Facebook](#), [LinkedIn](#), [Twitter](#), [Instagram](#) as well as [YouTube](#)) are fed constantly not only with the main results and news of the project but also with scientific articles, videos, and other multimedia resources closely related to the Blue Economy sector.

6.10.3 Briefings, Leaflets, and brochure

Digital and printable materials will be created to present the project activities, methodology and results in a brief and visually attractive way, ideal to be used during physical encounters with the target groups. These visual tools will be designed to be distributed among events, conferences, meetings, and trainings, for leveraging the exploitation potential of the project’s results and offerings.

6.10.4 Participation in Events, Workshops, and Conferences

All partners will organise/participate in several events aimed at disseminating the project activities and its results. The events can be formal and informal, aiming to encourage people of various backgrounds and disciplines to take part in the discussions. Other future events and direct contacts and meetings with stakeholders will be very important to promote the sustainability of the project results.

6.10.5 Partners’ networks

Exploitation activities will be mostly based on existing partner networks: all partners cooperate or are in close contact with the target users of the project results. All these target groups will be engaged to contribute to the project activities in all phases of the project.

6.10.6 Further improvement of project results

There is always space for improvement, especially in the actual globalized world. The technological proceedings and innovations, the market needs are continuously changing the sector. Partners will continue to uphold a transnational dialogue to keep updated on the BlueRev results.

6.11 Action suggestions for the partnership

6.11.1 Transfer and follow-up projects

Transfer enhances good practices by spreading results. The transfer can take place at all levels and the results can be used into new contexts or other organisations can customise the results to suit their conditions. And do not forget, submitting a proposal to a call for an exploitation project, can be a smart way of attracting more funding and a wider audience for your hard work. Follow up projects – after a project has finalised its results, it would be best sustained if partnership finds a way to build upon these results and expand the scope of what has already been achieved. Possibilities for doing this would be transfers of innovation or another form of continuation of completed projects.

6.11.2 Sustainability

Just because a project is completed, it does not mean its results disappear. It is important to keep them visible and available, especially through websites, so that target audiences can access them, learn from them, adapt them to their own needs and even build on them and take them to the next level. And of course, both transfer and commercialisation support sustainability. The continuity of the project started already very early when choosing the partnership! What to achieve, whom to reach and the stakeholders were clearly defined and established from the right beginning and if the target groups want and need the products, then the project will have a greater chance of survival after the end of the funding period! Where possible collect sustainable declarations, written and signed statements in which individuals/organisations explain how they intend to use/are using the products. If the declarations are obtained during the project's lifetime, the number can be an interesting indicator of the project's sustainability, and these are simultaneously clear exploitation evidence!

6.11.3 Accreditation and formal recognition of training

In the context of the project, under the training programs, materials, and certificates that will be prepared, it is important that the partners explore ways to make the training of trainers (as well as of the trainees) more formal, because in that way it can incentivise the joining of future participants to be specialised in using the project results and thus multiplying the implementation cases.

6.11.4 Networking/Lobbying

Influencing high-level change in policy and systems is a real possibility if project managers co-operate effectively and at the right levels. This is essentially a process of networking with all relevant stakeholders, so building contacts and attending meetings is vital – which is hard work but the only way. The European Commission, European and National Agencies, National Committees and Programme Committees organise events

to facilitate such co-operation. Attending events, such as conferences, seminars and debates, provides an ideal opportunity to showcase your results and also leads to fruitful contacts to enhance networking & lobbying. Some projects choose to hold some kind of European dedicated events (seminar, conference, workshop...), preferably in central EU venues, and with the involvement of relevant decision-makers, stakeholders, and funding entities. The events aim to convince the participants to introduce/take into account the products and approach of the project, which might be considered in policy formulation.

6.11.5 Develop New Partnerships

The long-lasting effects of co-funded projects can only be possible through effective partnerships, mostly as soon as the project is reaching its end. At this stage, most of the products are finalised and thus, it is easier to present a tangible resource to the project's stakeholders and show them how that specific product brings them benefits without costs.

6.12 Keep this in mind!

For a successful exploitation:

- The products and information should be in the right place but communicating the usefulness of the products is the key;
- Use the appropriate exploitation mechanisms as described;
- Incentives are important;
- Distribute the products to decision makers, opinion leaders and significant stakeholders;
- The deliverable message needs to fit the needs of the target groups;
- Be proud of the results and “keep the light burning” after the end of the project;
- In order to get better, never be satisfied;
- Create a business plan with further goals. Keep IPR in mind;
- It is important to keep yourself motivated and to network for your project/product even after its end. A very important success factor is the mind-set of the project team;
- Try to expand the target group. There is always the possibility for beneficiaries to become “new starters”;
- Successful exploitation needs to be supported by successful dissemination. The impact of the project needs to be described.

In general, BlueRev partners should always:

1. obtain and utilise end-user validation e.g. questionnaire analysis; evidence of effective use of outputs;
2. maintain products updated, upgraded based on ongoing feedback;
3. keep regular networking and lobbying activities;

4. update website's news constantly;
5. assure appropriate exploitation mechanisms;
6. keep regular contact with the relevant stakeholders.

7 Conclusions

In order to satisfactorily accomplish the main objectives of this dissemination and communication plan, the project needs to be promoted as a consistent brand with a strong mission towards strengthening the citizens' role in the blue bio-sector, supported by a useful set of tools, fed with professional and engaging content, and driven by fully committed and motivated partners.

During the first period of the project the main milestones have been achieved such as setting up the dissemination and communication tools and channels and carry out dissemination and communication activities such as updating the social media, newsletter, populate the channels with news and project updates and develop the first communication kit to present the project. These actions have contributed to increase the awareness about the project, which was able to satisfactorily reach a lot of its key performance indicators (KPIs).

The second period of the project will be crucial to achieve greater results for BlueRev' dissemination and communication which depends on strategic content feed and flow to relevant stakeholders using a multichannel approach. Thus, LOBA will be proactive and motivate all partners to contribute to the dissemination and communication of project results and share relevant content and information about BlueRev project among their networks and across channels.

The updated dissemination and communication plan is not final, and will be monitored and updated continuously, according to the natural evolution of the project and incoming opportunities during its development and promotion.

The results of the dissemination and communication activities will be reported in the progress reports for the Commission.

As far as exploitation activities are concerned, the BlueRev IPR management approach utilizes an IPR Matrix to define the main IPR issues concerning the BlueRev Innovation and IPR Management Strategy. This approach, supported by all project partners in identifying and managing the background, foreground knowledge and exploitable results of the project, allows to have a full overview of IP protection and necessary agreements to enable successful exploitation of the project's offerings.

The second part of the project will be crucial to plan more in depth an effective exploitation strategy, as more results will be made available and it will be possible to better understand how replicability of knowledge and tools generated can be guaranteed.

8 Appendix

Appendix A – Brand Manual

BlueRev

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

BlueRev

Negative version

This is the negative version of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN LOBA

BlueRev

Mono-chromatic

This is the monochromatic version of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

BlueRev

Claim version

This is the claim version of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN LOBA

02. size and guidelines

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN LOBA

BlueRev

Sizes and margins

	screen	print
with claim		
without claim		

Margins of the logotype

Margins of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN LOBA

BlueRev

Sizes and margins

Size of the logotype

Size of the logotype.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

03. colors and typography

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN LOBA

Blue color palette

niblick

Disruptive source to reinforce
the ocean concept.

The typography was all worked with some wavy
details as an association to the water concept.
We achieved a lettering with personality, robust
but at the same time, sober.

Use in very short titles and
large visual dimensions.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

LOBA

Minerva Modern

Elegant, formal and
corporate font.

Use in running text and longer titles.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

abcdefghijklmnopqrstuvwxyz
0123456789

ABCDEFGHIJKLMNOPQRSTUVWXYZ
0123456789

LOBA

04. graphics

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

BlueRev

graphics

The brand symbol brings together
various emerging concepts to the project.

The main case is the concept of water
as an association to the ocean, to the
layers of the sea, which is the
element that is base of the project.

The three lines can be associated with
the knowledge levels of the project
and the various actors involved in it.

The general shape of the symbol looks like
a square with rounded corners and this
reinforce the idea of care and solution.

CUSTOMER EXPERIENCE DESIGN

LOBA

Appendix B – Deliverable template

The image displays a grid of 16 thumbnail images representing the layout of a BlueRev deliverable template. Each thumbnail shows a page with the BlueRev logo and various content elements. The thumbnails are arranged in a 4x4 grid, with the last row containing three thumbnails and the last cell empty.

- Thumbnail 1 (Top Left):** Deliverable Title here and it may have three or four lines. Number of Deliverable.
- Thumbnail 2 (Top Row, 2nd):** Number of Deliverable. Deliverable Title here and it may have three or four lines. DELIVERABLE TYPE. MONTH AND DATE OF DELIVERY. WORK PACKAGE. LEADER. DISSEMINATION LEVEL. AUTHOR(S). DOI/ISSN.
- Thumbnail 3 (Top Row, 3rd):** Contributors. Reviewers. Revision History.
- Thumbnail 4 (Top Row, 4th):** Table of Abbreviations and Acronyms.
- Thumbnail 5 (Second Row, 1st):** Index of Contents.
- Thumbnail 6 (Second Row, 2nd):** Index of Tables.
- Thumbnail 7 (Second Row, 3rd):** Index of Figures.
- Thumbnail 8 (Second Row, 4th):** 1 Executive Summary.
- Thumbnail 9 (Third Row, 1st):** 2 Introduction.
- Thumbnail 10 (Third Row, 2nd):** 3 Section 1.
- Thumbnail 11 (Third Row, 3rd):** 4 Conclusions.
- Thumbnail 12 (Third Row, 4th):** 5 Appendix.
- Thumbnail 13 (Bottom Row, 1st):** 6 Landscape.
- Thumbnail 14 (Bottom Row, 2nd):** Consortium.
- Thumbnail 15 (Bottom Row, 3rd):** Consortium.
- Thumbnail 16 (Bottom Row, 4th):** Consortium.

Appendix C – PowerPoint template

Appendix D – Project brochure

The Oceans
cannot wait
and neither
can we.

**Join BlueRev
in promoting
a thriving Blue
Economy**

Take a deep dive with us and get to know more
about this project through www.bluerevproject.eu

Consortium

Funded by
the European Union
Views and opinions expressed are however those
of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect
those of the European Union. Neither the European
Union nor the granting authority can be held
responsible for them.

Contact Us
info@bluerevproject.eu
Follow Us
[f](#) [in](#) [t](#) [@BlueRev-EU](#)

**BlueRev **

A new
paradigm for
revitalising
blue economy
in local
communities

www.bluerevproject.eu

Welcome to BlueRev

A project funded by the EU Horizon Europe programme that aims to revitalise European local communities with innovative bio-based business, governance models, and social innovations focused on the blue bio-based sector.

BlueRev new paradigm will be piloted in 3 different European regions: Denmark & Greenland, Italy and Estonia.

We fight for

The development of innovative governance models to enable better-informed decision-making processes, societal engagement, and innovation.

The growth of small businesses, reaching consumers, through communication activities on innovation, climate neutrality, and the low environmental footprint.

Increasing the opportunities created by the local bio-based economy within broader bioeconomy transition.

More informed and engaged stakeholders, including primary producers and consumers.

Promoting novel business models to enable consumers, industry, and public bodies to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviours.

Identifying local actors and increase communication between them, showing opportunities for collaboration along the bio-based value chains.

Promoting social enterprise models, building on inclusiveness and cooperation within local communities, including low-income population.

Raising awareness among biomass producers, SMEs and civil society organisations, including NGOs, through tailored engaging activities and trainings.

Appendix E – Project Poster

BlueRev

Join BlueRev in promoting a thriving Blue Economy:
www.blurevproject.eu

Revitalising bio-based value chains

BlueRev will revitalise European local communities with innovative bio-based business, governance models, and social innovations focused on the blue bio-based sector.

Take a deep dive and discover this project while we set a new paradigm for revitalising Blue Economy and local communities.

Consortium

 Funded by the European Union

Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Contact Us
info@blurevproject.eu

Follow Us
 [@BlueRevEU](https://www.facebook.com/BlueRevEU)

Appendix F – Project promo card

BlueRev
Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

A new paradigm for revitalizing
Blue Economy and local communities

bluerevproject.eu Funded by
the European Union

Ignite your Journey of Collaboration
and Sustainable Growth in the
Blue Bio-based Economy

support-tool.bluerevproject.eu

Appendix G – Project Roll Up

BlueRev Join BlueRev in promoting a thriving Blue Economy: www.blurevproject.eu

Revitalising bio-based value chains

BlueRev will revitalise European local communities with innovative bio-based business, governance models, and social innovations focused on the blue bio-based sector.

We fight for

- The development of innovative, sustainable, and resilient governance models
- Increasing opportunities for collaboration among local actors
- Linking the valorisation of ecosystem and nature services with a sustainable production
- Promoting social enterprise models for local communities
- The growth of small businesses that focus on a low environment footprint
- Promoting stakeholders' integration in bio-based value chains
- Encouraging novel business models to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviours

Take a deep dive and discover this project while we set a new paradigm for revitalising Blue Economy and local communities.

Consortium

BlueRev is a project funded by the European Union under the Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme.

Contact Us: info@blurevproject.eu
 Follow Us: [f](#) [in](#) [t](#) [@blurevEU](#)

Appendix H – Project presentation

BlueRev
Revitalisation of European local communities with innovative business models and social innovation in the blue bio-based sector

Funded by the European Union

Key Elements

- Funding Scheme:** CSA – Coordination and Support Action
- Budget:** € 2 222 952,50
- Duration:** 3 years (1st September 2022 – 31st August 2025)

BlueRev Consortium

Coordinator: APRE, Food & Bio Cluster Denmark, LOBA

Partners: UTA University of Applied Sciences, RiSE, Eesti Maailikool, NIBIO

BlueRev Main Objective

BlueRev aims to select a range of systems in the blue bio-based sector in **3 different pilot regions** (Denmark, Italy and Estonia), to **tailor value chains** from valorisations of co-products as feedstock to processing/conversion to final products, in order to **revitalise local communities**, both in a territorial and social sense.

BlueRev Specific Objectives

SO1 To engage local communities of stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentials, to improve awareness of stakeholders and to improve communication between them about opportunities for collaboration along the bio-based value chain (WP2-5)

SO2 To analyse social and economic barriers and potentials in pilot regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new inferred governance and especially social innovations developed within the project (WP3-WP4)

SO3 To assess existing/develop new monitoring systems and indicators of the effectiveness of existing governance schemes, to analyse pilot regions and to allow replication across the EU (WP2-6)

SO4 To analyse and develop new or updated business models and local specific and innovation actors to enable societal impact and performance of the whole pilot regions value chains (WP3-WP4)

BlueRev Specific Objectives

SO5 Environmental footprint of the whole value chains of pilot regions, through LCA analysis (WP3)

SO6 To carry out a training programme to increase skilled jobs opportunities and small-scale establishments in the bio-based sector and to support the development of communication of innovation for small businesses and for business-to-consumers (WP3)

SO7 To reach a social impact of performed activities by involving all the stakeholders through a wide dissemination and awareness campaign (WP3)

BlueRev Concept and Methodology

- Analysis of local innovation process
- Analysis of business models
- Analysis of the governance model
- Environmental assessment
- Inventory of existing practices
- Stakeholders Board
- Local actors and business models
- Workshops, web-based platforms
- Case studies demonstration
- Training, Coaching programme
- Communication and Dissemination
- Multi-stakeholder approach
- 31 local workshops to involve stakeholders in all stakeholders
- 2 final case study guidelines for local businesses

BlueRev Pilot Regions

Partner	Region	Value chain	Stakeholders	Description
UITA	Denmark	Local co-products for production of feed and fuel	300+ members, including Companies producing high value added products from animal origin (e.g. fish, pig, poultry), Local authorities (Energy, Environment), The Municipality of Lemby (Municipality Government of Greenland)	The uptake of blue bio-based economy value chains poses a series related to lack of digital personal digital innovation being an innovation region (Greenland)

BlueRev Pilot Regions

Partner	Region	Value chain	Stakeholders	Description
		Use of food distribution and conversion systems	Stakeholders' network of 70+ stakeholders, including Companies and Researchers (e.g. VITA ID) - Developing legislation for business and manufacturers and a food network consisting of different substances (including system consultants, etc.) research and development organisations (e.g. ESB, Eircom, University of Life Sciences, Future Biorefinery of Technology) Local authorities (Liam Heneghan)	A transition from traditional technologies for processing and aging to modern technologies in order to reduce pathogens that could be harmful to other industries. To expand the scope of the bioeconomy in the region based on other local system resources, not only red algae but taking advantage of the experience gained in the other pilot regions. The main bottlenecks include: lack of skilled staff, specialists in the company and region. Gap in the connection between production and end-users in some industries.
		Water based bio-based compounds and degradation based on structural modification for research and commercial	ENEC includes 134 enterprises and 46 institutions, associations, universities, Research and culture centres, among which companies producing fish hydrolysis (e.g. Biotec, Biotec, ETC), University of Palencia, Research centre CIC 161, University consortium province of Valladolid and local stakeholders (Department of Mediterranean Fisheries of the State region, Confederación Triguera)	The main bottlenecks are represented by the lack of infrastructure and government resources/business models for collection, marketing and selling marine bio products and by the gap in the experience between production and end-users. The companies in the sector of cosmetics, nutraceuticals and pharmaceuticals.

Funded by the European Union

Overview of challenges in Pilot Regions

01 The lack of logistic infrastructures and governance measures/business models for collection, marketing and selling of marine bio products

02 A gap in the connection between production and end-users

03 Lack of skilled personnel and R&D specialists in the company and region

04 Being an outermost region (especially, Greenland)

05 A transition from traditional technologies to modern technologies

Funded by the European Union

BlueRev Expected Results

- 1 best practice guideline (WP4) and at least 3 demonstration workshops for the 3 pilot regions under study within the project. ~50-100 participants per workshop (WP5).
- A training programme that focuses on helping local stakeholders to develop skilled jobs and small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy: 4 modules for a total of 13 lessons for association of producers, master and PhD students, 100-200 participants in total, (WP5).
- 1 best Practice guideline supporting the development of communication of innovation for small businesses and for business-to-consumers (WP5).

At least 10,000 recipients of dissemination campaign. Numbers of stakeholders and activities targeted are reported in section 2.2-3.31 (WP5).

Funded by the European Union

BlueRev Expected Results

- Engagement of at least 300 stakeholders and 3 pilot regions (WP2)
- 1 Analysis Business models, governance structure and social measures of the 3 pilot regions under study within the project (WP3)
- Programme of at least 6 workshops in WP3 (3) and 4 (3) (at least 10 participants per each workshop aiming at helping local stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities in their regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new business models, informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project)
- At least 2 new models to identify or set-up social innovations to enable stakeholders to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviour and to advance the role of 'social enterprise' model for local communities (SAL) 1 New business model (B2C), 1 New governance model (D&C)

Funded by the European Union

BlueRev Workplan

Funded by the European Union

thank you

Funded by the European Union

BlueRev Consortium

Bio-based revitalisation of local communities

APRE

Food & Bio Cluster

LOBA

UiA

SE

Ensti Masouhhood

NIBIO

Funded by the European Union

@bluerevEU | bluerevproject.eu | info@bluerevproject.eu

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Appendix I – Project stationery kit

Raquel Nogueira
Project Manager
raquel@loba.com

blurevproject.eu
info@blurevproject.eu
f in @BlueRevEU

Appendix L – IPR Matrix (M18)

Background (BG): Information held by beneficiaries, owned or controlled by project partners and brought to the project; may come from existing knowledge as well as copyright or other IPR. According to the CA, Background is defined as “data, know-how or information (...) that is needed to implement the action or exploit the results”. Background information has to be:

- 1) Relevant to the project result,
- 2) needed to carry out the project or for using the foreground, and 3) somehow embedded in the result.

Background Number	Relevant Background	Contributing Partner (Partner Name)	Short Description of BG	Type of Protection (patent, copyright, ...)	How will it be utilised within BlueRev?	Conditions to Use within BlueRev? (free to use, licence fee, restrictions, NDA..)	Conditions to use outside BlueRev E.g. Is it confidential? Can it be shared with externals? Is it currently shared with externals? If yes, on what conditions?	Interest in further exploitation through BlueRev results (Yes/No)
BG1	Existing knowledge and know-how on project management and Quality assurance	APRE	development of tools to manage and monitor project progression; tools to manage risk assessment and quality assurance	Free to use	for the proper management of the project	free to use within the project	free to use within the project	no
BG2	Database of contacts	ALL	Extensive database of contacts of the consortium partners, as reported in Table 2.1 –Partners network and dissemination channels of the GA	Confidentiality agreements	Stakeholders' board structure (D2.1): The Stakeholders' board and database is used to inform about the project and it's activities; to mobilise & promote.	free to use within the project	Confidential	yes
BG3	Extensive networking ability (of the consortium)	ALL	Extensive networking of the consortium partners; Mutual collaboration with ongoing projects	Confidentiality agreements	To set up the stakeholder community and to engage, mobilise and coordinate stakeholder communities	free to use within the project	Confidential	yes
BG4	Existing knowledge and know-how of stakeholder community mapping and user research	NIBIO	NIBIO develops freely available map-services on the web as part of its mandate; NIBIO is dealing with social innovation and governance models in many project s	Confidentiality agreements	For the work to be performed in WP3. Template for stakeholder mapping, development of questionnaire	free to use within the project		

BG5	Existing knowledge in Social innovation	NIBIO	Main know how available for this project: NIBIO is dealing with social innovation and governance models in many project	Free to use	for work in WP3 and WP4	free to use within the project		
BG6	Existing knowledge in business models	UiA	Main know how available for this project: It will exploit the knowledge acquired in previous projects and activities to develop new of updated business models and will exploit its nature of being an high education institution to realise training activities	Free to use	for work in WP3 and WP4	free to use within the project		
BG7	Existing knowledge in Governance models and analysis	RISE	RISE has expertise in governance models and foresight. It will also exploit this expertise within the BlueRev project.	Free to use	for governance models in WP3 and WP4: RISE will develop a methodology to assess the effectiveness of the governance framework, i.e., the schemes, processes, and principles organising and surrounding the cases. The methodology will be tailored to the needs and local conditions of the cases while considering broader impact and replication potential of the governance schemes	free to use within the project		
BG8	Existing knowledge in LCA	RISE	RISE has expertise in LCA. It will also exploit this expertise within the BlueRev project. Background generated by the RISE research team directly involved in the BlueRev project according	Free to use	for LCA studies in WP3	free to use within the project	Use of RISE's Background for other purposes than for the implementation of the project must be negotiated separately with RISE	

			to: Non-confidential research results and non-confidential know-how relevant for execution of the project Non-confidential LCA datasets relevant for the execution of the project Licensed software and databases for LCA calculations needed for the execution of the project according to the terms and conditions specified by the relevant license agreement				at each individual occasion.	
BG9	Existing knowledge in business models	EMU	EMÜ develops business models and will exploit its nature of being an high education institution to realise training activities.	Free to use	for work in WP3 and WP4	free to use within the project		
BG10	Experience and know-how on training courses design and development	EMU	EMÜ is high education institution to realise training activities.	Free to use	For the implementation of workshops course in WP5: Design of a training course and implementation of different learning modules customised on target users training needs and expectations	free to use within the project		
BG11	Experience and know-how on training courses design and development	UNIPA	UNIPA is high education institution to realise training activities.	Free to use	For the implementation of workshops course in WP5: Design of a training course and implementation of different learning modules customised on target users training needs and expectations	free to use within the project		

BG12	Experience and know-how on biobased products	UNIPA	UNIPA is high education institution to realise training activities.	Free to use	For the mapping activities in WP3 and the implementation of workshops course in WP5: Design of a training course and implementation of different learning modules customised on target users training needs and expectations	free to use within the project		
BG13	Experience and know-how on training courses design and development	DFBG	DFBG has experience in the field of blue bio-based sector, and its strong collaboration among universities and companies, providing training activities to the stakeholders involved in the project.	Free to use	For the mapping activities in WP3 and the implementation of workshops course in WP5: Design of a training course and implementation of different learning modules customised on target users training needs and expectations	free to use within the project		
BG14	Experience and know-how on dissemination and communication	LOBA	LOBA will exploit the knowledge and the network gained in EU projects to lead dissemination and communication activities of the BlueRev project.	Free to use	in WP2 and WP6	free to use within the project		
BG15	Dissemination Networks	ALL	Extensive database of contacts and networking of the consortium partners, as reported in Table 2.1 – Partners network and dissemination channels of the GA; Mutual collaboration with ongoing projects	Free to use	in WP2 and WP6	free to use within the project		
BG16	Experience and know-how on dissemination	APRE	Main know how available for this project: Networking, stakeholders engagement and co-creation events	Free to use	in WP2 and WP6	free to use within the project	free to use within the project	yes

	and communication							
BG17	Experience and know-how on training courses design and development	APRE	APRE has considerable experience in training activities (courses, workshops, info-days, seminars and webinars, hosting study visits) in all fields of the Framework Programme (horizontal issues and thematic).	Free to use	For the implementation of workshops course in WP5: Design of a training course and implementation of different learning modules customised on target users training needs and expectations	free to use within the project	free to use within the project	yes
BG18	Experience and know-how on dissemination and communication	FBCD	FBCD will bring into the project the stakeholders of the bio-based sector value chains in Denmark, and their knowledge about social and economic barriers and potentialities. A significant experience in dissemination activities: organisation of and participation in European events, (see table 2.1).	Free to use	in WP2 and WP6	free to use within the project		
BG19	Experience and know-how on training courses design and development	UiA	UiA brings in know-how to entrepreneurship and training	Free to use	For the implementation of workshops course in WP5: Design of a training course and implementation of different learning modules customised on target users training needs and expectations	free to use within the project		

Foreground (FG) = Project Results, including information, being protectable or not, which are generated under the project; belongs to the beneficiary generating it. Can be jointly generated (joint ownership) and can be transferred (third parties).

FG n°	Work Package	Short Description of FG	Specific Proj. Res. as deliv.	Main Contributing Partner	Further Contributing Partner(s)	Related Background Number	Type of Protection	Conditions to Use within BlueRev	Interest in Further Commercialisation of BlueRev Results	Conditions to Use after the end
FG 1.1	WP1	Proper management of the project: Project well managed with data properly collected, processed, maintained and shared during and after the end of the project	D1.1	APRE	ALL	BG1	Free to use	Free to use	no	free to use
FG 1.2	WP1	Control of the quality of project results and management of risks: prompt identification of risks and its solution, required for a successful achievement of project objectives; guidelines for quality assurance and regular check that results and achievements are in line with the objectives.	D1.2	APRE	ALL	BG1	Free to use	Free to use	no	free to use
FG 2.1	WP2	Stakeholders' board structure	D2.1	APRE	LOBA	BG2	Free to use	Free to use	no	Confidential
FG 2.2	WP2	Engagement of at least 500 stakeholders and 3 pilot regions	D2.2	APRE	ALL	BG3	Free to use	Free to use	no	Confidential
FG 3.1	WP3	Map of existing monitoring systems on a case-study-basis to promote upscaling across EU	D3.1	NIBIO	UNIPA	BG 4; BG 12				
FG 3.2	WP3	Collection of relevant data for mapping the current governance structures, business models and social innovations linked to the implemented regions.	D3.2	NIBIO		BG 4				
FG 3.3	WP3	Identification of criteria for defining key performance indicators (KPI's) based on good practice principles	D3.3	NIBIO		BG 4				
FG 3.4	WP3	Analysis social and economic barriers, commonalities and potentialities to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behavior	D3.4	RISE		BG 7				
FG 3.5	WP3	LCA report on the pilot regions: Environmental assessment of the pilot regions identified, through LCA analysis	D3.5	RISE	UNIPA	BG 8; BG 12				
FG 3.6	WP3	Analysis of business models and local capacities and innovation actors	D3.6	UiA		BG 6				
FG 3.7	WP3	Programme of at least 3 workshops in WP3 (at least 10 participants per each workshop) aiming at helping local stakeholders to analyse social and		NIBIO	ALL	BG 3-18				

		economic barriers and potentialities in their regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour through new business models, informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project.							
FG 4.1	WP4	New models for social innovations to enable stakeholders to switch to socially and environmentally responsible behaviour: the assessment of the depth of change of the social innovation involved in the pilot regions and the news ways proposed to switch stakeholders' behaviour to socially and environmentally responsible and to achieve 'social enterprise' i) assess the social values of the identified social innovations (WP 3); ii) evaluate how these social innovations interplay with other types of innovation; iii) co-create novel ways of generating specific value for society based on social-experimentation, structure, capacity and constraints through dialogue (in close collaboration with task 4.2).	D4.1	NIBIO	UiA	BG 5;			
FG 4.2	WP4	New business models: new or improved business models, including models for the pilot regions. According to the analysis performed in Subtask 3.3.2, new or improved business models for the pilot regions will be developed, considering different business model approaches and best practice from related branches as described in section 1.2.1.5. The business models will be finalised with a co-creative approach in task 4.2 by collecting input from stakeholders coming from pilot regions.	D4.2	UiA	EMU	BG 6; BG 9			
FG 4.3	WP4	New governance models: Development of governance innovation, including new models for the pilot regions, describing possible opportunities for how governance innovation can help the cases going from today and towards their future visions. RISE will analyse possible opportunities for how governance innovation can help the cases going forward from today and towards their future visions. Recommendations for governance, strategy, and new models at organisational, local, regional, national, and international level will be given, if applicable, for each of the pilot region. Also, potential implications of the recommendations for the existing governance framework will be presented.	D4.3	RISE	NIBIO	BG 7; BG 5			
FG 4.4	WP4	A best practice guideline including the best practices coming from the 3 pilot regions	D4.4	UIA	ALL	BG 3-19			
FG 4.5	WP4	Programme of at least 3 workshops in WP4 (3) (at least 10 participants per each workshop) aiming at helping local stakeholders to analyse social and economic barriers and potentialities in their regions to enable the transition towards socially and environmentally responsible behaviour		ALL	ALL	BG 3-18			

		through new business models, informed governance and especially social innovation developed within the project.							
FG 5.1	WP5	Training programme and materials to increase skilled jobs opportunities and small-scale establishments in the bio-based sector; A training programme that focuses on helping local stakeholders to develop skilled jobs and small-scale establishments in the bioeconomy: Multimedia contents and a demonstrative videos for best practices demonstrated will be prepared and made available to the stakeholders on the project website. FBCD, DFBG EMU will provide all the facilities and ensuring the proper execution, while all other partners will be involved in the contents definition	D5.1	FBCD	ALL	BG 3-18			free to use
FG 5.2	WP5	Multimedia contents and demonstrative videos for best practices demonstrated	D5.2	LOBA		BG 14			free to use
FG 5.3	WP5	Lessons recordings and related materials: collections of recordings and related materials in order to assure the guideline dissemination	D5.3	DFBG	ALL	BG 13			free to use
FG 5.4	WP5	Guidelines for small business on how to communicate: Guideline (translated in the 24 official EU languages) for small business to improve their skills on how to communicate innovation, climate-neutrality and low environmental footprint/benefits/trade-offs and performances of bio-based products and services	D5.4	APRE	LOBA	BG 16, BG17; BG 14			free to use
FG 6.1	WP6	D6.1 Plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication activities	D6.1	LOBA	ALL	BG 14			free to use
FG 6.2	WP6	D6.2 Updated plan for dissemination and exploitation including communication	D6.2	LOBA		BG 14			free to use
FG 6.3	WP6	D6.3 Final Exploitation and replication plan	D6.3	APRE		BG3; BG 16, BG17			free to use
FG 6.4	WP6	ON Line Platform-		LOBA		BG 14			

Exploitable Results (ER): Direct or indirect utilisation of foreground in further research activities (other than those covered by the project) or for developing, creating and marketing a product, a process or a service. An exploitable result is defined as an outcome of the project (achieved or expected) that meets two conditions:
 (i) It has commercial/social/academic relevance
 (ii) It can be commercialised/exploited as a standalone result (product, process, service, etc.) (a patent for licensing is also an exploitable result)
 These results might need further R&D, prototyping, engineering, validation, etc. at the end of the project – before they become commercially exploitable. Exploitable results are generally defined as products, processes, services, methods, etc., which are new, improved or more efficient.

ER number	Exploitable Result (ER)	Short Description	Main Partner (s)	Contributing Partners	FG number (related)	BG number (related)	Proposition for ER - Owner (if any)	Relevance for IP protection (if any)	M - Making them and selling them	U - Using them	L - License them	S - Providing as a Service	O - Others	Most promising path	Further Comments (Please insert any further comments that you might have)
ER1	Online platform	The project's online platform (task 6.3), will be an Open Space that will contain all materials developed within the project, including multimedia contents and a demonstrative videos for best practices demonstrated, lesson	LOBA	ALL	FG 6.4	BG14									

		<p>recordings and related materials, best practices guidelines etc. and standard info i.e. project and partners, calendar of events, news, etc., by facilitating cross-sector collaborations among stakeholders in the bio-based economy and to provide a knowledge centre to share relevant project results. A web-based platform able to facilitate cross-</p>																
--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

		sector collaborations among stakeholders in the value chains of the biobased economy will be set-up to provide a knowledge centre to i) share relevant information, to ii) make stakeholders aware about the possibilities offered by the uptake of the bioeconomy, ii) enhance cooperation opportunities, iii) train stakeholders, iv) allow collaboration and documents																
--	--	---	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--	--

		exchange among stakeholders.													
ER2	Guidelines	Guidelines reporting the best practices demonstrated in pilot regions	UiA	NIBIO; RISE; EMU;	FG 4.4	BG 5-10									Articles in journal/newspaper/magazine specific for primary producers; publications in journals; posters/presentations in international conferences.
ER3	New business models	Novel business models, models for social innovations	UiA	EMU	FG 4.2	BG 6; BG 9									Articles in journal/newspaper/magazine specific for primary producers; publications in journals; posters/presentations in international conferences.
ER4	Training programme and materials	Training programmes	FBCD	ALL	FG 5.1	BG 3-18									Articles in journal/newspaper/magazine specific for primary producers; publications in journals; posters/presentations in international conferences.
ER5	Guidelines for small business on how to communicate	Guidelines supporting the development of communication	APRE	LOBA	FG 5.4	BG 16, BG17; BG 14					X		X		Use of the project results: Project materials, such as new business, governance models and models for social

Bio-based revitalisation
of local communities

Consortium

Funded by the European Union. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

www.blurevproject.eu info@blurevproject.eu

@BlueRevEU

